

SOiLO-LiVE

SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY
OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES

D7.11

Annual sustainability report

Date: 14/01/2025

Version: 2.0

Deliverable 7.11 Annual sustainability report

Document Information

Project title	SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES
Project acronym	SOIL O-LIVE
Grant Agreement	101091255
Work package	WP7 - Outreach, dissemination and communication
Deliverable number and title	D7.11 Annual sustainability report
Deliverable description	Annual sustainability summary project report
Deliverable type	R-Document, report
Dissemination level	PU-public
Lead beneficiary	DEOLEO
Due submission date	31/12/2023
Submission date	05/05/2025

Document Author(s) and Reviewer(s)

Name	Entity	Role (author, reviewer)
Bartolomé Lara Cledera	Deoleo	Author
Juan Carrasco Vilchez	Deoleo	Reviewer

Document history

Version	Date	Made by	Short Description of Changes
1	17/04/2024	Juan Carrasco Vilchez	first edition of the document
2	14/01/2025	Juan Carrasco Vilchez	second edition of the document

Table of Contents

Document Information	2
Table of Contents	3
Executive Summary	4
SUSTAINABILITY PROJECT REVIEW 2023	5
SUSTAINABILITY PROJECT REVIEW 2024	43

Executive Summary

Within the framework of WP7 (Outreach, dissemination and communications), a sustainability protocol has been developed, which includes sustainable practices applicable to olive groves and oil mills.

This document shows the results of the implementation of the practices included in the sustainability protocol in olive groves and oil mills in different territories. It is a report on the work carried out by Deoleo technicians in this implementation during 2023 and 2024.

The report details the improvements in the different olive groves and oil mills, monitoring data and implementation of all the blocks of the protocol, as well as practices that have a positive impact on social and economic aspects, quality and, of course, the environment.

This report is produced annually and also includes the implementation of the protocol in olive groves and oil mills that are not part of the Soil O-live project, but which Deoleo carries out with its own funding.

SUSTAINABILITY PROJECT

REVIEW 2023

Ed:1.0

25/01/2024

INTRODUCTION

Deoleo's sustainability project involves developing a sustainable chain for olive oil production, which ensures traceability from the olive tree to the table, protects the environment, respects biodiversity, local communities and promotes the practice of fair working conditions. The project is based on the UN's 17 Sustainability Goals. This document presents the results of the **implementation of the project during the year 2023**.

OVERALL RESULTS IMPLEMENTATION 2023

The sustainability project began its implementation in July 2018 with 11 oil mills belonging to the cooperative group (VIÑAOLIVA), in total, this Extremadura group is made up of about 4,500 members and the associated hectares are about 25,000. Six months later, 13 more oil mills joined of the ALMALIVA group, a group from Córdoba made up of 13,000 members and which has 76,000 hectares of associates.

Currently, the number of affiliated mills has increased considerably, **at this time there are 82 mills/cooperatives, in Spain, Portugal, Italy, Tunisia, Greece and Argentina**.

During the year 2023, new suppliers from the InterOleo group have joined the sustainability project, with new oil mills, 2 new suppliers from Tunisia, 4 from Greece, 2 from LATAM, 2 from Jaencoop, which represents an incorporation of 3,780 new partners and 21,351 new hectares, adding a total since the beginning of the project of: 52,153 farmers and 292,749 hectares of olive groves.

Map. Location of the oil mills in Spain and Portugal.

Location of oil mills in Italy

Location of oil mills in Greece

In this year 2023, 2.420 hours of advice have been used by Deoleo technicians distributed throughout all the oil mills that are part of the project. Especially in JAENCOOP, VIÑAOLIVA, ALMALIVA, INTEROLEO and TUNISIA. Also noteworthy is that during 2023, 77 implementation visits have been carried out and 10 GAPs have also been carried out (2 GAPs in Italy, 4 in Greece and 3 in Spain (2 in Jaencoop and 1 in InterOleo))

Compared to 2022, the hours spent by Deoleo technicians in consulting, pre-audits, internal and external audits have significantly increased, despite the setbacks that have arisen this year, where due to organizational changes, those responsible for implementing the sustainability had to assume other responsibilities, despite these changes, the hours used in 2023 have been 2,420 hours.

The average time spent by technicians on visits and direct implementation with suppliers has also increased compared to previous years. In 2020, the hours per technician were 489, while in 2021 and despite COVID, the hours per technician have increased to 906 hours, doubling the number of hours compared to the previous year. In 2023, despite the organizational changes of the organization, the ratio of hours per technician has been increased to a total of 1,474, taking into account the consideration of (1.5 technicians). 35 external certification audits have been carried out in Spain, Portugal, Italy, Tunisia, Greece, LATAM, 21 of them have been for recertification, 14 in new locations, all of them in different oil mills, which means that 100% of The oil mills that are within the project, in addition to

being audited internally, have been audited externally by Intertek.

During 2023, pre-audits have been carried out, prior to carrying out the certification audits, a novelty that was included in 2020, with the objective of measuring the work of implementing the protocol by Deoleo technicians and preparing the external audit. In 2023, 20 pre-audits have been carried out, corresponding to 256 hours.

During 2021, visits to farms of members of each cooperative began, in which personal interviews were carried out with farmers and questionnaires were carried out to obtain information in order to complete the mapping of each cooperative and propose actions. (Ex: workshops) most necessary for each of them. These visits also reinforce the presence of Deoleo technicians in the field. In total, 244 questionnaires have been carried out in 2023,

adding to the data from previous years, we have a total sampling of 479 members, with this characterization, a sampling has been obtained in 2023, of 2.250,35 Has (2023), 15,4% Organic , 22,55% Integrated production, 62,05% Conventional Olive Grove.

Adding the data of hectares visited in 2023 to those of previous years, the total number of hectares visited by Deoleo technicians is approximately 16.582,99 hectares, which represents 5,43% of the total hectares under the project.

To contextualize this data, it must be noted that the hectares/member ratio in the olive groves attached to the project is

approximately 5,71 hectares per member, and taking into account that this data includes the visit to some of the majority partners in some oil mills. , this means that to increase the percentage of hectares visited in a short time, the number of visits that must be made is very high.

Regarding the visited hectares of intensive and traditional olive groves in the different groups, it has increased considerably, visiting in 2023 “2.250,35 hectares, there is a total of 16.582,99 hectares, visited since the sustainability project began. All of this in another year of exceptional circumstances with organizational changes.

It should be noted that we currently have **52.153 farmers, covering an area of 292.749 hectares of olive groves.**

% Of Olivar visited by groups in 2023

INTERNAL INDICATORS

With all the information that Deoleo technicians have collected during this year 2023 and what had already been obtained in previous years, a series of indicators have been compiled to measure the performance of the oil mills and to be able to concentrate efforts and schedule actions for to next year. These indicators are divided into 4 large blocks: Organization and people, Food Quality and Safety, management of resources and waste, and finally use of agrochemicals, biodiversity and soil.

Organization and people:

A notable improvement can be observed in all parameters, it can be concluded that the oil mills have assumed sustainability within their company policies and have improved their organization in terms of investment planning, strategic plans, cost calculations, improvement of computer security and maintenance, also highlighting from the social point of view, the equality part, the % of oil mills with equality plans has gone from 2% to 24% since the beginning of the project, and the great improvement in regards to preparation

of training plans and coordination of business activities, as well as the recognition of social benefits, which, although they were carried out in practice, were not recognized as such in a documentary manner. New this year, the sustainability protocol has been updated, incorporating the study of new indicators. During the year 2023. It has been achieved that 93% of the cooperatives participating in the sustainability project define sustainability managers within their organizations. 24% of the suppliers adhering to the protocol have also taken some action in favor of equality in the last 3 years. During the year 2023, 100% of the suppliers adhering to the protocol have been able to carry out inventories of their service companies, further highlighting the importance of working with local communities.

*All indicators refer to the percentage of Mills that meet the requirements

QUALITY AND FOOD SAFETY:

This sector includes the production and food safety part in the oil mill. The percentage of oil mills with food hoses is 100% in 2023, currently we have 63.4% of oil mills that have all food bands. In this year, in which the new checklist has been implemented for a very short time, it has been possible to go from 46,3% to 90,24% of oil mills have the certificates of conformity of the stators. Furthermore, 81,7% of them have identified chemical hazards in the HACCP. The number of mills with magnets has also increased, the number of mills that have or have installed some mechanism to prevent the passage of vehicles over the reception hoppers, currently being 84,14% of the mills that have them (increasing by 16,14%), cleaning and/or maintenance records that the oil mills did not have or improved traceability have also been implemented, such as the record of the batch of talc used, all of them indicators referring to food safety.

Regarding the quality in the production of EVOO, at the beginning of the project there was a lack of control and records of fundamental parameters for quality and that allow us to know the weak points to take measures, there has been a very notable increase in the oil mills that have began to record the temperature of the dough (44 to 100%) and oil output in the centrifuge (26 to 95,1%), the mixing time (10 to 97,6%), and others such as the recording of temperatures in the winery. The registration or control of the time spent in the hopper of the olives was carried out by 8% at the beginning of the project, now that percentage has risen to 100%.

Resource and waste management:

This sector includes the efficient management of resources (Water and Energy), as well as the correct management of waste and recovery of by-products.

In this area, the oil mills at the beginning of the project had a very high margin for improvement, only 20% of them recorded water consumption and 14% had some type of savings plan, now in 2023 97,56% record water consumption. water and have a water savings plan, regarding energy the figures are similar, now 82,92% have a savings plan and 97,6% record their energy consumption, both outside and during the campaign. Despite being a new requirement, it has been achieved that 47,56% of the oil mills carry out meter readings, or define objectives for reducing water consumption.

Although all the oil mills reuse the olive pits for the boilers, they valorize the alperujo by taking them to the pomace mill, with regard to waste management, the oil mills, in all the member groups, had a very high deficiency, only 16% managed its waste correctly and almost half were not registered as producers of small waste. In 2023, all the oil mills are already registered as small producers and have a contract with an authorized waste manager, the management of this waste and their storage has also improved significantly, 100 % of the oil mills have their waste well stored and managed. During this year

2023, 32,92% of oil mills have implemented training in waste management, 6,097 % of oil mills manage firewood and 9,75% have compost plants.

Use of agrochemicals, biodiversity and soil:

One of the keys, probably the most important to reducing the use of agrochemicals in olive groves and thus preventing the loss of biodiversity, is the importance of each oil mill having an independent field technician who advises members on their treatments, as well as issue prescriptions for authorized agrochemicals with controlled and rational

doses, at this point since the beginning of the project 7 technicians have been hired by the groups, In 2023 this number has not changed, highlighting the commitment on the part of the Jaencoop group and the Almaliva Group.

Additionally, the issuance of recipes and bulletins by field technicians to members has been improved, the number of cooperatives attached to an API (integrated production) has increased, field notebooks have been updated, and the carrying out soil analyzes on the farms to know the state of the soil.

During this year 2023, training sessions have been held to promote the use of plant cover, prevent soil erosion, preserve the biodiversity of olive groves, use of by-products such as compost, etc. Carrying out a total of 17 workshops within the framework of the Soil O-live project and 5 in collaboration with the UPA, adding up to a total attendance of 595 farmers.

At the field level, the changes are much more difficult, since they often affect cultural changes, the establishment of the vegetation cover continues to be a pending issue, as well as other actions related to the fight against soil erosion and the restoration or conservation of biodiversity, to advance in this sense, we have concentrated the measures in the biodiversity plans, which in this year 2023 have reached all the oil mills, they have been updated, with commitments by the groups and oil mills to carry out concrete measures and with an execution date (Below is attached as an example measures proposed in the Jaencoop biodiversity plan)

These measures range from the establishment of vegetal covers, actions for reforestation with native flora, installation of nesting boxes or insect hotels, holding training sessions...etc.

Example:

Jaencoop

Biodiversity

Plan

PLAN DE ACCIÓN PARA LA CONSERVACIÓN DE LA BIODIVERSIDAD EN EL OLIVAR

Funded by the European Union

5º. Convertir zonas limitrofes en focos de biodiversidad.	Continuo	El uso indiscriminado de herbicidas, ha provocado que no exista vegetación arvense, incluso en márgenes de caminos, riveras, lindes... manteniéndose únicamente en lugares de difícil acceso	Mantenimiento de cubiertas vegetales arvenses permanentes, en zonas sin aprovechamiento agrícola.	Se pretende que al menos 1 socio de cada cooperativa que integran el grupo JAENCOOP fomenta y conserve los linderos en la campaña 2023/2024.
6º. Colocar elementos funcionales como hábitáculo para la fauna.	Continuo	El actual sistema de aprovechamiento agrario fomenta la destrucción de los refugios naturales de la fauna, tales como madrigueras, oquedades, etc.	Prescindir en la medida de lo posible de labores que alteren el perfil del terreno y realizar refugios artificiales para los casos en los que la regeneración natural no sea suficiente	Instalar cajas nido para aves insectívoras y rapaces. Instalar refugios para murciélagos. Instalar hoteles de insectos para polinizadores. Instalar puntos de agua para aves, anfibios e insectos acuáticos. El objetivo para la campaña 2023-2024 es que al menos 1 socio de cada cooperativa fomenta este tipo de acciones.
7º. Corregir cárcavas y arroyos transformándolos en zonas de alto valor en biodiversidad.	Continuo	Debido a las pendientes del terreno y la carencia de cubiertas y vegetación, se han producido cárcavas y arroyos de gran magnitud.	Transformar cárcavas y arroyos en zonas con alto valor en biodiversidad, empleando para ello gaviones y vegetación.	Conseguir que un 1% de los socios que tengan problemas con cárcavas, instauren vegetación/gaviones en cárcavas o arroyos para su control dentro de las explotaciones para el año 2023.
8º. Fertilización fundamentada en materia orgánica	Continuo	Uso de fertilización inorgánica como principal fuente.	Fertilización fundamentada en materia orgánica	JAENCOOP tiene una compostadora con residuos de alperujo de las cooperativas. Fomentar el picado de la cubierta vegetal y fomentar el asesoramiento técnico continuado con el fin de reducir el uso de abonos inorgánicos. Como acción se propone también fomentar el uso de compost por parte de los socios en la campaña 2023/2024

Also noteworthy is that 68,26% of suppliers have already installed functional elements for fauna in one of their partners' farms. It should also be noted that 59% of the cooperatives have some member in API.

STATUS BY GROUPS/MILLS

This section will analyze and detail key people in each oil mill and farmers, the degree of involvement of the oil mills, and practices that can be extrapolated to other groups or oil mills will also be identified.

GENERAL

During this year, a constant and progressive improvement has been noted in all groups, from the GAP to the external audit. During 2023, 25 internal audits have also been carried out (4 Viñaoliva, 5 Almaliva, 8 Jaencoop, 7 InterOleo, 1 Italia)

GOOD PRACTICES IN FIELD

Good practices carried out on some of the farms participating in the project are shown below. Only images of the certified/visited oil mills in 2023 are shown.

PRACTICE	EVIDENCE	PRACTICE	EVIDENCE
Planted Roof (S. Coop del Campo San Isidro, Valencia del Ventoso)			
Maintenance of the vegetation cover (S. Coop Ntra Sra de la Cabeza, Fuente del Maestre)			
Creation of a sustainability space (Olivarera Santa Marina de Aguas Santas, Fernán Núñez)			

<p>Manure application (Subbética oil mills)</p>			
<p>Gully correction (Olivarera de los Pedroches)</p>			
<p>Installation of solar panels on farms (SCA Labradores y Ganaderos, Albendin)</p>			
<p>Installation of insect hotels and nest boxes (SCA Agraria Cerro Gordo)</p>			
<p>Planting vegetation cover in the center of the street (SCA Olivarera and Cerealista San Sebastian)</p>			

<p>Application of compost on member farms (SCA San Isidro de Loja, Granada)</p>				
<p>Installation of artificial feeders (Aceites de Sierra de Yeguas)</p>				
<p>Installation of Insect Hotel (Our Lady of Guadalupe, Úbeda)</p>				
<p>Installation of solar panels (SCA los Toscares, Venta de los Santos)</p>				
<p>Conservation of boundaries (SCA San Juan de la Cruz, Beas de Segura)</p>				

<p>Conservation of tall trees (SCA La Vicaria, Puente Génave)</p>			
<p>Vegetative cover (SCA San Blas, Sorihuela del Guadalimar)</p>			
<p>Installation of nest boxes (SCA Santa Teresa de Jesús, Beas de Segura)</p>			
<p>Installation of insect hotels (SCA Bedmarese)</p>			
<p>Maintenance of the vegetation cover (SCA San Gines and San Isidro, Sabiote)</p>			

<p>Conservation of the stone walls (SCA San Isidro, Pozo Alcon)</p>			
<p>Conservation of boundaries (Roldan Oliva, Íllora)</p>			
<p>Conservation of unproductive areas (SCA Ntra Sra de la Asunción, Orcera)</p>			
<p>Gull control (SCA San Juan, Villargordo)</p>			
<p>Pruning debris chopping (SCA Ntra Sra del Rosario)</p>			

<p>Installation of irrigation probes (Olivomundo)</p>			
<p>Reforestation with poplars (Molino del Genil)</p>			
<p>Organic olive grove (Mavrogenis)</p>			

GOOD PRACTICES IN THE OIL MILL

Below, some of the good practices carried out in Almazara in 2023 are presented through images.

VIÑAOLIVA			
MILL IMPROVEMENT	AND EVIDENCE	MILL IMPROVEMENT	AND EVIDENCE
<p>Designation of Sustainability responsible (San Isidro, Entrin Bajo)</p>			

<p>Installation of food belts (Viñaoliva, Almendralejo)</p>			
<p>Installation of solar panels (San Isidro, Valencia del Ventoso)</p>			
<p>Responsible designation for sustainability (S. Coop Cristo del Humilladero, Medina de las Torres)</p>			
<p>ALMALIVA</p>			
<p>Installation of electric charging points. (Santa Marina de Aguas Santas, Fernán Núñez)</p>			
<p>Installation of awareness-raising posters (Mill of Luque)</p>			

<p>Updated training plan (Our Lady of Luna, Villanueva de Córdoba)</p>			
<p>Good water consumption practices (Our Lady of Consolation, Doña Mencía)</p>			
<p>Carbon footprint calculation (SCA Cerro Gordo, Ventorros de San José)</p>			
<p>Courtyard remodelling project (SCA Olivarera and Cerealista San Sebastián)</p>			
<p>Budget for the realization of the carbon footprint (SCA Olivarera de Lucena)</p>			

JAENCOOP			
<p>Installation of infographics (SCA Ntra Sra de Guadalupe, Úbeda)</p>			
<p>Emergency Plan (SCA San Francisco, Villanueva del Arzobispo)</p>			
<p>Definition of objectives for water and energy savings (SCA Vera Cruz, Villanueva del Arzobispo)</p>			
<p>Appointment of a workers' representative (SCA San Francisco, Arroyo del Ojanco)</p>			
<p>Access control registration (SCA Cristo de la Salud, Villargordo)</p>			

<p>Inclusion of HACCP chemical hazards (SCA San Blas, Sorihuela del Guadalimar)</p>			
<p>Remodelling of the olive reception courtyard (Aceites el Carrascal)</p>			
<p>MOLINO DEL GENIL-FITAGRO</p>			
<p>Installation of retention trays on the mills to prevent contamination. Molino del Genil</p>			

PURICON SCA			
<p>Puricon SCA</p> <p>Reception Courtyard Improvements</p>			
ACEITES DE SIERRA DE YEGUAS			
<p>Oils from Sierra de Yeguas.</p> <p>Filtration performance.</p>			
INTEROLEO			
<p>Explanatory infographics in the courtyard (Bedmareense SCA)</p>			
<p>Improvement in technical advice (SCA San Gines and San Isidro, Sabiote)</p>			
<p>Request for a quote for the installation of solar panels (SCA San Isidro, Pozo alcón)</p>			

<p>Improvement in waste management (Roldan Oliva, Illora)</p>			
<p>Installation of food belts (SCA Ntra Sra de la Asuncion, Orcera)</p>			
<p>Contract for the installation of a photovoltaic plant (SCA Oleícola Baeza)</p>			
<p>Covered reception hoppers in the field (Almazara la Loma)</p>			
<p>Installation of new food belts (SCA Union Oleicola Cambil)</p>			
<p>Implementation of the infographics of Deoleo's sustainability project (Kapnas SA)</p>			

WORKSHOP IN MILL SUSTAINABILITY PROJECT

During the year 2023, 17 Workshops have been held in different cooperatives adhered to the sustainability project within the framework of the European Soil O-Live project and 5 more Workshops in collaboration with UPA. Below is a summary table of the Workshops:

JAENCOOP			
SCA SAN MARCOS, BEAS DE SEGURA			
SCA LA UNIÓN DE CHILLUEVAR, CHILLUEVAR			
SCA SAN ISIDRO LABRADOR, BENATAE			
ALMALIVA			
ALMAZARAS DE LA SUBBETICA			

<p>SANTA MARINA, FERNAN NUÑEZ</p>			
<p>SCA SAN ISIDRO DE LOJA</p>			
<p>INTEROLEO</p>			
<p>OLEOCAMPO, TORREDEL CAMPO</p>			
<p>SCA SAN ISIDRO DE LOJA</p>			
<p>VIÑAOLIVA</p>			
<p>VIRGEN DE LA ESTRELLA, SANTOS DE MAIMONA</p>			

WORKSHOP IN COLLABORATION WITH UPA

CAÑADA DEL ROSAL, SEVILLA

CASTILBLANCO, BADAJOZ

CUEVAS DE SAN MARCOS, MÁLAGA

**Sostenibilidad
y digitalización**
Claves para el futuro
del sector olivarero

PROGRAMA CUEVAS DE SAN MARCOS
10:00 BIENVENIDA: • Francisco Olivares, Secretario General de UPA Málaga • 14 de septiembre de 2023
• Respaldo de UPOJOL 10:00 horas
11:00 MANEJO DE EMERGENCIAS VEGETARIAS: José Alfonso Correas Gilero, Director de Agricultura Sostenible JAS-COR 10:00 horas
11:00 DIGITALIZACIÓN: CAMBIO DIGITAL DE EXPLOTACIÓN: Juan Regalado Blasquez, Técnico de UPA Málaga
11:30 NOVEDADES DE ASPECTOS LABORALES Y SU APLICACIÓN EN EL OLIVAR: María Angélica Ortega Durán, Responsable de Empleo de UPA Andalucía
12:00 CLAUSURA: Cristina Cano Martín, Secretario General de UPA Andalucía

deoleo UPA MÁLAGA

www.upamálaga.es

LA NAVA DE RICOMALILLO

ALMALIVA

The Almaliva group entered the project in 2019, after four years, it can be said that the involvement is maximum, the staff is fully involved and they have a team of field technicians who make it easier to carry out the measures included in the biodiversity plan, as well as the reduction of the use of agrochemicals.

Thanks to Deoleo's sustainability protocol, the hiring of new field technicians has been achieved. The 4 cooperatives recertified during 2023 have improved their organizational document structure, have improved in the management of hazardous and non-hazardous waste, and in the integration of records within the quality system, obtaining optimal results AA Gold in all cases, it must also be considered that this year, the sustainability protocol has been restructured. In this year 2023, the field characterization has been enhanced, visiting a total of 244.59 hectares, carrying out follow-ups in all the group's cooperatives. Likewise, farm evaluation checklists are being prepared to know the area of ecological interest of the farms, 7 pilot farms are being selected. New farms will be selected annually and measures will be implemented to improve biodiversity on these farms.

STRENGTHS: INVOLVEMENT and PROACTIVITY, AGROCHEMICALS (team of technicians), BIODIVERSITY.

WEAK POINTS: FOOD SAFETY (this part is being reinforced in some oil mills with technical advice).

OBJETIVOS ESTABLECIDOS PARA LAS MEDIDAS DE CONSERVACIÓN DE LA BIODIVERSIDAD.

Cooperativa:

- 1º. Asesorar y transferir conocimientos a los agricultores y
- 2º. No emplear herbicidas o usar el mínimo posible.

	Asesorar y transferir conocimientos a los agricultores.		No emplear herbicidas o usar el mínimo posible.	
	Nombre de los cursos de asistencia de los técnicos.	Cálculo del porcentaje de incremento o decremento con respecto a la campaña anterior	Nombre de los cursos dados a los agricultores	Cálculo del porcentaje de incremento o decremento con respecto a la campaña anterior
Objetivos realizados en la campaña 2021/2022	DF-INNOVA. Regeneración de suelos, fertilización, y mejora eficiencia en la fertilización nitrogenada. 15/11/2022	100 % (covid en campaña anterior)	REDUCCIÓN APLICACIÓN HERBICIDAS Regeneración de suelos, reducción de herbicidas y mejora eficiencia. 15/11/2022	100 % (covid en campaña anterior)
Objetivos propuestos para la campaña 2022/2023	- Charla de cubiertas vegetales. - Charla abonado. - Mejora eficiencia de riego		-Charla de reducción del uso y mejora en la eficiencia de aplicación de herbicidas.	

Example: Almaliva Revision Act.

1. INDIQUE EL NÚMERO, LONGITUD O SUPERFICIE DE CADA ELEMENTO SIE									
Type de SIE	*Condiciones principales (consulte las condiciones precisas para cada tipo) *	"Cantidad y unidad" (tenga cuidado de no contar dos veces entre hectáreas -ha-, son -a- y centiare -ca)				Fact. Conv.	Total (m ²)		
Setos o franjas leñosas	Ancho máximo ≤ 10 m	0				m lineal	10	0	
Arboles aislados	Couronne ≥ 4 m OU arbre têtard					árbol (s)	30	0	
Árboles alineados	*Cada árbol respeta las condiciones Árbol aislado (ver arriba) Y espacio entre coronas mínimo de 5 m *	0				m lineal	10	0	
arboledas	Superficie ≤ 10 áreas	0	ha	0	a	0	ca (=m ²)	1,5	0
	10 áreas < superficie ≤ 30 áreas	0	ha	0	a	0	ca (=m ²)	1,5	0
Estanques	*No artificializado (ni hormigón ni plástico) Y superficie máxima ≤ 10 áreas	0	ha	0	a	0	ca (=m ²)	1,5	0
Zanjas	*No artificializado (ni hormigón ni plástico) Y ancho máximo ≤ 6 m *	0				m lineal	6	0	
Paredes de piedra tradicionales	*Piedra natural sin hormigón Y 0.5 m ≤ altura ≤ 2 m Y 0.1 m ≤ ancho ≤ 2 m *	0				m lineal	1	0	

Cheklst Ecological Focus Area

MILL	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
FERNAN NUÑEZ	CREATING A SUSTAINABLE GARDEN
LA SUBBETICA	CARBON FOOTPRINT CALCULATION THROUGH THE MINISTRY'S CALCULATOR
LUQUE	HAZARDOUS WASTE TREATMENT CONTRACT
POZOBLANCO	COMPOSTING PLANT.
VILLANUEVA DE CÓRDOBA	HIRING A QUALITY TECHNICIAN.
BUJALANCE	INSTALLATION OF AN ELECTRIC CHARGING POINT
CASTRO DEL RÍO	CREATION OF A COMPOSTING PLANT IN THE LAST YEAR.
DOÑA MENCIA	IMPROVED TECHNICAL ADVICE TO PARTNERS IN COLLABORATION WITH ALMALIVA
LA VICTORIA	TRAINING IN WASTE MANAGEMENT AND PURCHASE OF A NEW BIOMASS BOILER.
ALBENDIN	INSTALLATION OF A NEW WASHING MACHINE IN PATIO
CERRO GORDO	CALCULATION OF THE CARBON FOOTPRINT THROUGH FAECA
NUEVA CARTEYA	REMODELING OF THE OLIVE RECEPTION COURTYARD
SAN SEBASTIAN DE LOS BALLESTEROS	COURTYARD REMODELING PROJECT
OLIVARERA DE LUCENA	INSTALLATION OF ELECTRIC CHARGING POINTS, CREATION OF AN API
SCA SAN ISIDRO, LOJA	INSTALLATION OF SOLAR PANELS

JAENCOOP

This group is a clear example of excellence in quality, thus promoting the early harvest, with some own brands such as Prologo or Saqura. Likewise, in 2023 the Biodiversity Plan has been reviewed, with 5 technicians hired by the group. This year, it should be noted that the technical advice has been extended to more cooperatives in the group (Olivar de Segura).

The 6 cooperatives recertified during the 2023/2024 campaign have improved significantly in waste management, organization of the cooperative, records of oil quality parameters and commitments to specific actions to improve, and with the support of Deoleo and Jaencoop technicians, their recertification has been achieved. During the year 2023, all the oil mills already certified in previous years have been monitored, and, in addition, 8 internal audits have been carried out

As a novelty, it is also worth highlighting the great advances made at the level of biodiversity, already the Jaencoop group during this year 2023, has collaborated with the Elige Vida foundation, The purpose is to create sustainable spaces in the oil mills, this year actions have been developed in the certification and

recertification cooperatives. These spaces will be a reservoir of fauna, so important to curb climate change and reduce negative impacts. On the one hand, the aim is to create a sustainable garden, where a wide variety of native plants (predominantly aromatic and scrub) are included

that simulate a small forest. This garden will attract insects as important as pollinators. These insects will help attract species such as birds.

These Sustainable Spaces have been created in the cooperatives certified in this year 2023 (SCA La Unión de Chilluevar, SCA San Juan de la Cruz, SCA Los Toscares, SCA San Juan Bautista, SCA San Francisco, Aceites el Carrascal, SCA San Isidro, Iznatoraf, Aceites Zarate). It should also be noted that pre-audits have been carried out on the oil mills that are due for recertification.

During this year 2023, the characterization of the field has also continued, visiting the farms of farmers belonging to the group, adding a total, in 2023 alone, of **442.38 hectares**.

Also, during 2023, the biodiversity plan of the JAENCOOP group has been revised with the inclusion of 2 new oil mills.

INFORME ACTUACIONES REALIZADAS PARA LA “ACTUALIZACIÓN Y SEGUIMIENTO DEL PLAN DE BIODIVERSIDAD” JAENCOOP 2023	
FECHA	30 de junio de 2023
ALMAZARA	GRUPO JAENCOOP 2º GRADO SCA
ASISTENTES	PROJAEN <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JUAN MARTOS LORITE • LAURA FERNÁNDEZ LÓPEZ • JOSÉ VERA • JOSE MANUEL MARTINEZ MEDINA • MARIO ANAYA VIVO

Image: Jaencoop Biodiversity Plan Review

STRENGTHS: INVOLVEMENT, PROACTIVITY, ORGANIZATION, FOOD SAFETY, BIODIVERSITY, TECHNICAL ADVICE IN THE FIELD.

WEAK POINTS: Residues (There are still some oil mills in an initial phase of management, they should continue to improve in this aspect), Water (There are many irrigation communities that do not grant the relevant consumption to farmers), Volume of EVOO due to climatic conditions.

MILL	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
NTRA SRA DE GUADALUPE	AN OCCUPATIONAL RISK PREVENTION DELEGATE HAS BEEN DEFINED
NTRA SRA DEL PILAR	HIRING A NEW SUSTAINABILITY OFFICER
SCA SAN FRANCISCO VVA	ISO 22000 CERTIFICATION
SCA SAN ISIDRO VVA	CREATING A SPACE FOR SUSTAINABILITY
VERA CRUZ VVA	COMPUTERIZED TRACEABILITY SYSTEM
LA UNION DE CHILLUEVAR	HIRING OF A NEW PROJECT MANAGER AT THE OIL MILL
LOS TOSCARES, VENTA DE LOS SANTOS	INSTALLATION OF SOLAR PANELS ON THE FARMS OF SOME MEMBERS
SAN FRANCISCO, ARROYO DEL OJANCO	TECHNICAL TRAINING IN PAC
SAN ISIDRO DE IZNATORAF	100% SUBSTITUTION OF FOOD BELTS
SAN JUAN DE LA CRUZ	APPLICATION OF ORGANIC AMENDMENTS ON THE FARMS OF SOME MEMBERS
ACEITES ZÁRATE	RECEIVING HOPPERS COVERED IN THE LAST YEAR
GUTAMARTA	INSTALLATION OF SOLAR PANELS AND IMPROVEMENTS IN THE RECEPTION HOPPERS TO PREVENT THE PASSAGE OF VEHICLES OVER THEM
LA VICARÍA	REMODELING OF THE ENTIRE RECEPTION COURTYARD
NTRA SRA DE NAZARET	COLLABORATION WITH THE EUROPEAN PROJECT SOIL O-LIVE, WHERE ACTIONS ARE BEING CARRIED OUT ON PARTNER FARMS (APPLICATION OF BIOCHAR, SOIL ANALYSIS, STUDIES OF PLASTICS IN SOIL, ETC.)
SAN BLAS, SORIHUELA DEL GUADALIMAR	GETTING STARTED IN FIREWOOD MANAGEMENT

SAN ISIDRO LABRADOR, BENATAE	INVESTMENT IN NEW LAND FOR FACTORY EXPANSION
SAN MARCOS	CREATION OF A HAZARDOUS WASTE MANAGEMENT POINT
SANTA TERESA	CARBON FOOTPRINT STUDY
CRISTO DE LA SALUD	TRANSPORT AND FARM MANAGEMENT SERVICES TO MEMBERS
ACEITES EL CARRASCAL	REMODELING OF THE RECEPTION COURTYARD
SCA SAN JUAN BAUTISTA	GETTING STARTED IN HAZARDOUS WASTE MANAGEMENT

INTEROLEO

The InterOleo group entered the sustainability project in 2021, with a total of 7 certified oil mills. Despite the difficulties encountered, during 2023, this number has been increased by 4 more mills, adding a total of 16 certified mills in 2023. One of the strengths that has been achieved with the protocol is the hiring of a quality manager by InterOleo, highlighting improvements in quality after the completion of the GAP, and unification of registration formats. During the year 2023, 1 GAP has been carried out in addition to follow-ups in those certified in 2022, as well as implementation visits in the others to achieve certification. As a novelty at InterOleo, internal audits have been carried out on the certified oil mills in 2020, developing a total of 7 internal audits. It is also worth mentioning the realization of 4 Workshops. Another of the great advances made with the group is the updating of the biodiversity plan at the group level, including the new cooperatives, despite the fact that the countryside continues to be its main weak point, as it does not have hired field technicians. Also, it is worth noting the great progress made in waste management, when we started working with the group, most of them did not properly manage waste, this year in the oil mills certified in 2022 improvements have been detected in this aspect, however, in the new oil mills of 2023, this has continued to be the weak point.

The review report of the biodiversity plan has also been updated with the measures implemented in 2023.

OBJETIVOS ESTABLECIDOS PARA LAS MEDIDAS DE CONSERVACIÓN DE LA BIODIVERSIDAD. REV2 - 16/11/2023										
OPERATIVA	CAMPAÑA	1ª. Asesorar y transferir conocimientos a los agricultores.	2ª. No emplear herbicidas o usar el mínimo posible.	3ª. Inocular y diversificar las cubiertas vegetales.	Datos relacionados con la superficie en ecológico.	4ª. Expandir y conservar zonas con alto valor ecológico y biodiversidad.	5ª. Convertir zonas limítrofes en focos de biodiversidad.	6ª. Colocar elementos funcionales como hábitats.	7ª. Corregir cárcavas y arroyos transformándolos en zonas de alto valor.	8ª. Fertilización orgánica.
	CURSOS DE ASISTENCIA DE LOS TÉCNICOS	3 JORNADAS ASISTENCIAS REALIZADAS EN SCA LA BIODIVERSIDAD: SCA OLEOCAMPO, SCA NITRA SPA DE LOS RINCONES.	FORMACIÓN TÉCNICA EN BIODIVERSIDAD Y CUBIERTAS VEGETALES AUMENTAR SUPERFICIE EN API	SUPERFICIE DE ECOLOGICO Y Nº DE SOCIOS	Nº DE EXPLOTACIONES DE LAS DIEZ EXPLOTACIONES	% DE SOCIOS-NOMBRE IN	% DE SOCIOS CON NOMBRE QUE HAYAN AUMENTADO UN 2%	% DE SOCIOS CON NOMBRE QUE HAYAN AUMENTADO UN 2%	PLANTAS DE COMPOSTAJE O REALIZACIÓN DE MULCHING	
PO INTEROLEO	OBJETIVOS REALIZADOS CAMPAÑA 2022/2023	En el contexto de administración y en el contexto de nuestro se ha dado formación a todos nuestros socios sobre Proyecto de olivos resiliente y sostenible.	En estas jornadas se potenciaba la gestión de cubiertas vegetales teniendo en el uso de variedades en casos extremos	4 Workshop en SCA San Glicer & San Isidro, Sca Los Rincones, SCA Obispa Baza & SCA Oleocampo Incorporación de socios en el proyecto de sostenibilidad de Oleo en API	Socio nuevo en Ecológico	Oleocampo de Sierra Bercubierta vegetal (SCA BIODIVERSIDAD, SCA Mira, Sca de Los Rincones, SCA San Isidro de Frasco (Nueva). Las que está en producción integrada 70% con cubierta vegetal.	SOCA DE LA SCA LA BIODIVERSIDAD - María Valdivia Muñoz - creación de cubierta vegetal	SOCA DE LA SCA LA BIODIVERSIDAD - María Valdivia Muñoz - Actualización se está mejorando los indicadores de biodiversidad por técnicas del proyecto para implementar.		
	OBJETIVOS PROPUESTOS PARA LA CAMPAÑA 2023/2024	Difusión del proyecto junto a diputación de Jaén en los distintos municipios de la provincia.	Difusión del proyecto junto a diputación de Jaén en los distintos municipios de la provincia.	Aumentar la superficie API Y Nº DE SOCIOS O SUPERFICIE DE AGRICULTORES QUE HAYAN IMPLEMENTADO ESTAS MEDIDAS	aumentar la superficie un 2%	aumentar la superficie un 2%	AL MENOS 1 SOCIO NUEVO	AL MENOS 1 SOCIO NUEVO	EN ESTUDIO	

Image: InterOleo Biodiversity Review

Another of the considerable improvements to highlight is that, during 2023, farm visits have continued to be carried out, therefore conducting interviews with farmers, and adding a total of **718.53 hectares, in 2023 alone, doubling the number of hectares visited in 2022, so there has been a considerable improvement in this aspect.**

STRENGTHS: ORGANIZATION, FOOD SAFETY.

WEAK POINTS: PROACTIVITY, Teamwork and improved communication are necessary to address the certification of the next cooperatives. Another of their weak points is biodiversity, although they have improved compared to previous years, due to the fact that they are collaborating with other organizations such as Seo Bird Life, in some oil mills.

MILL	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
Bedmareense SCA	Collaboration with Seo Bird life for the implementation of measures in favor of biodiversity.
Ntra Sra de los Remedios, Jimena	Creation of a new phytosanitary warehouse.
San Gines y San Isidro, Sabiote	Collaboration agreement with BALAM for technical advice
San Isidro Labrador de Canena	Installation of irrigation probes in the olive groves of some members.
San Isidro, Pozo Alcón	Installation of some belts for food use
Almazara la Loma SL	Purchase of new, more efficient machinery in the field.
Oleocampo SCA	Improvement in the cleaning system, through a specialized company.
SCA La Union de Bujalance	Improvements to the conditioning of the patio.
Roldan Oliva	Getting Started in Hazardous Waste Management
SCA Ntra Sra de la Asunción, Orcera	Participation in Equality Conferences.
SCA Oleícola Baeza	Start of project for photovoltaic installation.
SCA San Juan, Villargordo	Getting started in firewood management
SCA Union Oleícola Cambil	Implementation of a belt replacement plan
SCA Ntra Sra de la Misericordia	Getting Started in Hazardous Waste Management
SCA SAN FELIPE APOSTOL	Improvement in the management of hazardous and non-hazardous waste
SCA NTRA SRA DEL ROSARIO, CHARILLA	Improvement in the traceability system (records of frozen olives, chopped, etc.)

VIÑAOLIVA

Despite the limitations in terms of the characteristics of the soil in the area, farmers who want to improve their agri-environmental practices are being located, in 2023, all the cooperatives of the group have been monitored, detecting in some of them a considerable increase in olive groves with vegetation cover, in cooperatives such as (Cristo del humilladero and Coop del Campo San Isidro, Valencia del Ventoso, and Cristo del Arco Toral).

Cooperatives that initially did not manage their waste properly have all now have a contract with a waste manager, and the segregation of their waste, both hazardous and non-hazardous, has been greatly improved. Considerable improvements to highlight is that, in 2023, functional elements for fauna have been

installed in the cooperatives that were due for recertification.

As a novelty this year, internal audits have been carried out, making the new sustainability protocol known to the associates. 4 internal audits have been carried out. It should also be noted that one of the cooperatives has abandoned the sustainability project (LTDA Hornachos), as a result of this during 2023 we have not continued working on the Seo Bird life project that we had with Viñaoliva. It is also worth mentioning the composting plant that has been built by the Cooperativa de la Estrella, an activity that should serve as a beacon to be followed by the others, a cooperative very committed to sustainability, stating that it is going to create a Biodigestator in 2024.

Improvements to be highlighted are that, this year, review of the biodiversity plan of the cooperatives that have had to renew the sustainability project have been carried out.

And as a novelty, it should be noted that 2 Workshops have been held in collaboration with Soil O-live in Viñaoliva, Almendralejo and Los Santos de Maimona. These days will be extended in 2024.

	<p>REVISIÓN PLAN BIODIVERSIDAD VIÑAOLIVA</p>	<p>FECHA DE EDICIÓN: 07/11/2023</p>	
<p>1. CUBIERTA VEGETAL/ MINIMIZACIÓN DEL LABOREO</p>		<p>Más allá de continuar con la colocación de nidos de elegir a 17 agricultores para que empezaran a hacer menos laboreo y dejar capa libre natural.</p>	
<p>2. COLABORACIÓN CON ASOCIACIONES</p>		<p>Colaboracion con asociaciones a favor de la igualdad como la Jornada de Socias en Viñaoliva. Proyecto Seo Bird life se encuentra estancado.</p>	
<p>2. COLABORACIÓN CON</p>		<p>Se ha colaborado con Deoleo, y el proyecto Soil Olive de la Universidad de Jaen, en la celebración de 2 Workshop de asesoramiento a los socios, en Almendralejo y Los Santos de Maimona, para todos los socios que forman parte de Viñaoliva https://soilolive.eu/farmers-</p>	

Image: Example of the minutes of the review of the Viñaoliva biodiversity plan

As an improvement, it should also be noted that during this year 2023, field characterization has continued, conducting interviews with farmers, adding up to a total of **286.18 Ha visited in 2023 alone.**

STRENGTHS: AGROCHEMICALS, TECHNICAL ADVICE.

WEAK POINTS: BIODIVERSITY and SOIL (Seo BirdLife agreement// HORNACHOS), PROACTIVITY AND COMMITMENT.

MILL	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
SAN ISIDRO, ENTRIN	CONDUCTING COACHING TRAINING
SANTA MARTA	INSTALLATION OF SOLAR PANELS
VIÑAOLIVA	DATA AUTOMATION WITH ADAPTED SOTWEARE
VIRGEN DE LA ESTRELLA	PROJECT FOR THE CREATION OF A BIODIGESTATOR
NTRA SRA DE LA CABEZA	IMPROVED HAZARDOUS WASTE MANAGEMENT
NTRA SRA DE PERALES	ISO 9001 CERTIFICATION
SAN ISIDRO, VALENCIA DEL VENTOSO	COVER SOWN ON THE FARMS OF SOME MEMBERS
SAN ISIDRO, VILAFRANCA	IMPROVEMENT OF THE RECEPTION YARD AND IMPROVEMENT IN TECHNICAL ADVICE, AGREEMENT WITH CAMPOVIVO
CRISTO DEL HUMILLADERO	TRAINING IN EQUALITY, NEW FARMS WITH GREEN COVER
CRISTO DEL ARCO TORAL	START IN WASTE MANAGEMENT CONSULTING

SIERRA DE YEGUAS

It is worth noting during 2023, the hiring of a new manager and head of sustainability. During the year 20223, some farmers have been located who have left vegetation cover during the year 2023. During the visit carried out in 2023, some farmers with planted vegetation cover were visited.

It has been possible for the oil mill, which did not have any record of both quality and management, to begin to collect quality data, such as churning temperatures, centrifuge, churning times, dwell times in the hopper, talc, etc. The cooperative, thanks to the protocol, has started in the management of hazardous and non-hazardous waste, as well as has managed to process the change of water supply to the municipal network, making a contract with a supply company in 2023. Also during 2023, the field characterization has been enhanced, adding a total of 119 Ha visited in 2023.

STRENGTHS: BIODIVERSITY (clear willingness of partners and management to carry out actions)

WEAK POINTS: vegetation cover (at the end of the year due to climatic conditions), RESOURCE MANAGEMENT.

MILL	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
ACEITES DE SIERRA DE YEGUAS	PLANTED VEGETATION COVERS, IMPROVEMENTS IN WATER OPTIMIZATION.

PURICON

Despite being ISO 9001 and ISO 14001 certified, improvements have been made to the quality management system, such as updating the maintenance plan or getting temperatures and times to be studied during milling, and even considering taking a quality management course. In 2023, the recertification of the cooperative has been achieved, with significant improvements such as the signing of the biodiversity plan, or the communication of the right to collective bargaining.

STRENGTHS: AGROCHEMICALS (API available) and WASTE.

WEAK POINTS: BIODIVERSITY and SOIL (area with little vegetation cover) / PROACTIVITY, We need staff involvement.

MILL	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
PURICON SCA	MOST OF THE PARTNERS ARE IN API, ISO 9001 CERTIFIED, ISO 14001.

MOLINO DEL GENIL-FITAGRO

It is worth highlighting the work of the quality manager, who is very attentive and always ready for improvement actions. The group continues its commitment to sustainability, developing actions such as reforestation with poplars, which is an example of revaluation of a flood-prone area with a high risk of erosion, an action that can clearly be extrapolated to other cooperatives or groups.

It also highlights the improvement in waste management, as this was one of its weak points to date, as well as the initiation of records of quality parameters.

It is also worth mentioning in Sobrado the excellent management of resources (Water and Energy) that since the beginning of the project has been extended to the oil mill part.

In this year 2023, in Sobrado, remote monitoring has been carried out, where they state that new olive grove farms have been purchased. An internal audit will be carried out during 2024. A workshop is also planned for 2024.

STRENGTHS: AGROCHEMICALS (GLOBAL GAP), FIELD RESOURCE MANAGEMENT (SENSORS), ORGANIZATION, QUALITY AND FOOD SAFETY.

WEAK POINTS: FUTURE RISK OF HAVING TO RECONVERT THE OLIVE GROVE.

MILL	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
SOBRADO	IRRIGATION MONITORING (IRRIGATION PROBES)
MOLINO DEL GENIL	COMMITMENT TO SUSTAINABILITY (REFORESTATION WITH POPLARS)

OLIVOMUNDO

The involvement of the whole team has been very good from the beginning, its facilities are magnificent, and some quality parameters that are not measured were updated, a biodiversity plan was developed. During 2023, remote monitoring has been carried out, due to the fact that the recertification was at the end of 2022. An internal audit is planned during 2024.

As implemented actions, a sustainability manager (Joao) has been defined, and training has been carried out on the sustainability protocol. In the field, it should be noted that reforestation has been carried out on the banks of the stream with aromatic species.

STRENGTHS: AGROCHEMICALS (GLOBAL GAP), WATER MANAGEMENT, ORGANIZATION, QUALITY AND FOOD SAFETY.

WEAK POINTS: ENERGY MANAGEMENT.

MILL	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
OLIVOMUNDO	GLOBAL GAP, WATER MANAGEMENT

GREECE

During 2023, the possibility of enlargement to new countries was explored, studying the possibility in Greece. So, during the month of March, Deoleo's Head of Sustainability travelled to Greece, where 4 GAPs were carried out in Greece, in the areas of Heraklion, Chania, Messinia and Peloponnese, four strategic areas, in the oil mills (Kapnas SA, Gargaliani, korbakis and Mavrogenis, belonging to the Psaroudakis group).

During the month of November, members of Deoleo's sustainability team travelled to Greece to carry out the pre-audits, carrying out 4 and 4 certification audits, achieving the certification of the 4 oil mills with the AA Gold level of conformity.

Strengths: AGROCHEMICAL MANAGEMENT (ORGANIC OLIVE GROVES)

Weak points: WASTE MANAGEMENT (THERE ARE NO WASTE MANAGERS IN THE COUNTRY), ORP (IT HAS BEEN COMPLEX IN SOME AREAS), FOOD SAFETY.

ITALY

During 2023, 3 internal audits have been carried out in Italian oil mills (Petritzeli, D'Adatto, and Eurocoop), in addition to follow-ups to those already certified, were carried out during the first part of the year.

In terms of quality, maintenance plans, operational records of temperatures and churning times, reduction of the storage time of the olives have been drawn up. In all of them, records of water and energy consumption have also been compiled.

It is also noteworthy that in this year 2023, work is being done on the certification of two new oil mills, one belonging to UNAPOL (Casale), and another belonging to CONFOLIVA (Carmen), for them, the GAP has already been carried out, with the help of members of the pool of auditors and work is being done on the

certification. Certification audits will be conducted in early 2024.

STRENGTHS: BIODIVERSITY, AGROCHEMICALS AND WASTE

WEAK POINTS: ENERGY MANAGEMENT and FOOD SAFETY

MILL	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
BITONTO	OPTIMIZED WATERING WITH PLAN
EUROCOOP	OPTIMIZED WATERING WITH PLAN
DE PALMA	Exclusive Field Technician Project
PETRIZZELLI	REUSE OF THE ALPEORUJO AS FERTILIZATION
D'ADDATTO	COVERED RECEPTION PATIO
CASALE	STORAGE OF OLIVES IN BOXES TO AVOID SPOILING
CARMEN	ORGANIC OLIVE GROVES

2023 AUDIT SCORES SUMMARY

This year, and despite the scenario in which we are moving of volume shortage and poor harvest, all the proposed and planned oil mills have been certified, with 93.8% of the certified mills obtaining the AA Gold conformity level, and 3.1% the AAA Platinum conformity level, only one mill has obtained the A Silver conformity level.

Graph: % sustainability project audit scores 2023.

GRUPO	ALMAZARA	PUNTUACION
VIÑAOLIVA	S.COOP SAN ISIDRO, VILAFRANCA DE LOS BARROS	GOLDEN
VIÑAOLIVA	S.COOP CRISTO DEL ARCO TORAL, HINOJOSA DEL VALLE	SILVER
VIÑAOLIVA	S.COOP CRISTO DEL HUMILLADERO, MEDINA DE LAS TORRES	GOLDEN
JAENCOOP	SCA SAN FRANCISCO, VILLANUEVA DEL ARZOBISPO	GOLDEN
JAENCOOP	SCA SAN FRANCISCO, ARROYO DEL OJANCO	GOLDEN
JAENCOOP	SCA SAN JUAN DE LA CRUZ, BEAS DE SEGURA	GOLDEN
JAENCOOP	SCA LA UNION DE CHILLUEVAR, CHILLUEVAR JAEN	GOLDEN
JAENCOOP	SCA LOS TOSCARES, VENTA DE LOS SANTOS	GOLDEN
JAENCOOP	SCA SAN JUAN BAUTISTA, PEÑOLITE	GOLDEN
JAENCOOP	ACEITES EL CARRASCAL, TORRES DE ALBANCHEZ	GOLDEN
JAENCOOP	SCA SAN ISIDRO, IZNATORAF	GOLDEN
JAENCOOP	ACEITES ZARATE, TORREPEROGIL	GOLDEN
ALMALIVA	SCA VIRGEN DE LA TORRE LA VICTORIA	GOLDEN
ALMALIVA	SCA JESUS NAZARENO	GOLDEN
ALMALIVA	SCA CERRO GORDO, VENTORROS DE SAN JOSE	GOLDEN
ALMALIVA	SCA LABRADORES Y GANADEROS, ALBENDIN	GOLDEN
ALMALIVA	SCA NTRA SRA DEL ROSARIO, NUEVA CARTEYA	GOLDEN
ALMALIVA	SCA OLIVARERA Y CEREALISTA SAN SEBASTIAN, SAN SEBASTIAN DE LOS BALLESTEROS	GOLDEN
MOLINO DEL GENIL	MOLINO DEL GENIL, ECIJA	GOLDEN
ACEITES DE SIERRA DE YEGUAS	ACEITES DE SIERRA DE YEGUAS	GOLDEN
PURICON	PURICON SCA, AGUADULCE	GOLDEN
INTEROLEO	SCA SAN FELIPE APOSTOL, BAEZA	GOLDEN
INTEROLEO	NTRA SRA DEL ROSARIO, CHARILLA	GOLDEN
INTEROLEO	ROLDAN OLIVA	GOLDEN
INTEROLEO	SCA NTRA SRA DE LA MISERICORDIA	GOLDEN
GRECIA	KAPNAS	GOLDEN
GRECIA	MAVROGENIS	GOLDEN
GRECIA	KORBAKIS	GOLDEN
GRECIA	GARGALIANI	GOLDEN
AOG	ALL PACK	GOLDEN
AOG	UNIÓN AGRARIA	GOLDEN
TUNEZ	HUILERIE HOR	GOLDEN
TUNEZ	HUILERIE GOOC	GOLDEN
ITALIA	BITONTO	PLATINUM
ITALIA	DE PALMA	GOLDEN

Graph: Summary of scores obtained by Deoleo sustainability project during 2023.

PROJECT Soil O-live

Project to assess the biodiversity and functionality of European olive groves and their relationship with olive oil production and quality.

SOIL O-LIVE, led by the University of Jaén, aims to analyze the impact of pollution and land degradation on olive grove soils in terms of multi-biodiversity, investigate the relationship of the state of soil health with the quality and safety of olive oil; implement effective soil amendments and ecological restoration practices and define rigorous ecological thresholds to enable future standards to be implemented and clear regulations to design a novel certification for healthy soils in European olive groves.

The project, coordinated by the University of Jaén, has a consortium made up of 17 partners and has funding of almost 7 million euros within the framework of the Soil Health and Food Mission of the R+D+i Horizon Europe programme (the European Union's framework programme for research and innovation for the period 2021-2027). In January 2023, Deoleo's sustainability team attended the kick off meeting held at the University of Jaén, where the project was presented.

During this year 2023, active work has been carried out on the project, with the celebration of 17 workshops in different locations in Andalusia and Extremadura, with the active participation of 595 farmers.

Some of these conferences have had media repercussions in regional media such as Canal Sur, Día de Córdoba, ABC, etc.

News of interest disclosure:

[Deoleo celebra 17 formaciones a agricultores en 2023 para fomentar la producción sosten... \(cordobabn.com\)](https://www.cordobabn.com/)

<https://acceso360.acceso.com/deoleo/es-ES/?mod=TrackingPressViewer&task=default&external=1&companyNewsId=859750622&newsDate=1686780000&sig=b0c8b872bd0b0621a76a31a07169afc902ef14d3808524a44842b9552f692aa8>

<https://acceso360.acceso.com/deoleo/es-ES/?mod=TrackingPressViewer&task=default&external=1&companyNewsId=859750629&newsDate=1686780000&sig=8e2b33f1fe7e0fadd1b40eefadd3d5af6f581ab83647ec0b7871adbde9ba5d68>

During 2024, it is planned to continue with the realization of more conferences in collaboration with the project.

SUSTAINABILITY PROJECT

REVIEW 2024

Deoleo[®]
The Olive Oil Company.

Ed:1

14/01/2025

INTRODUCTION

Deoleo's sustainability project involves developing a sustainable olive oil production chain that guarantees traceability from the olive tree to the table, protects the environment, respects biodiversity and local communities, and promotes fair working conditions. The project is based on the 17 UN Sustainability Goals. This document presents the results of the implementation of the project during 2024.

GENERAL RESULTS IMPLEMENTATION 2024

The sustainability project began its implementation in July 2018. The purchase volume from the suppliers with whom the project was initially started, in the 18/19 campaign with sustainable oil, accounted for 23% of the volume of total EVOO purchased by the company. We currently have **88 olive mills certified** in the sustainability project, covering an area of **59,693 Members and 338,284 Has of Olive Groves**. During 2024, new suppliers in Spain (Oleand Manzanilla Olive with two centres and Aceites Canoliva S.L), new suppliers in Italy (Casale and Carmen), and in Chile the supplier Agrícola MonteOlivo have joined the sustainability project, and work is underway on the certification of new suppliers in Chile and Argentina, specifically with the suppliers (Aceitera Argentina, Finca la Bella, Servicios Neuquinos, Olivares de Quepu and Siracusa).

The volume represented by all sustainable oil mills in the 2023-2024 campaign is **39.04 %**, **11,32% more than in the previous campaign**, taking into account the two bad campaigns we have just gone through.

In the graph above, we can see that the main sustainable suppliers for the 2023_2024 campaign have been Viñaoliva, Almaliva and Molino del Genil in Spain, Lagar do Sobrado in Portugal.

Below are some plans showing the locations of the oil mills that are part of the sustainability project

Map. Location of olive oil mills in Spain and Portugal.

Location of olive oil mills in Italy

Location of olive oil mills in Greece

In 2024, **2,080 hours of advice have been spent by Deoleo technicians** spread across all the oil mills that are part of the project. In particular, the time invested in advice in the main Spanish groups stands out (Jaencoop 25.2% InterOleo 20.4%, Almaliva 19.1%, Viñaoliva 12.5%). It is also worth noting that, during 2024, 90 follow-ups have been carried out, 13 more than in 2023.

In 2024, **22 internal audits** were carried out, which meant 352 hours invested by sustainability technicians in internal audits. Also, **7 GAPS have been carried out**, 2 in Spain, specifically with the suppliers Oleand Manzanilla Olive and Aceites Canoliva S.l, and the remaining ones in Chile and Latam, specifically with the suppliers (Servicios Neuquinos, Finca la Bella, Aceitera Argentina, Olivares de Quepu and Siracusa), which have involved 112 hours of advice on GAPS.

Despite being a lower percentage, since they are isolated oil mills and the weight is less than that of large groups, 88 hours of advice have been provided to suppliers Oleand Manzanilla Olive and Aceites Canoliva S.L.

Regarding the hours of advice spent in 2024, 2080 hours were provided by sustainability technicians. If we put this figure into perspective per technician, it was 832 hours per technician in 2024, with the availability of 2.5 technicians, since the Sustainability Manager/Director is not 100% dedicated to advice and implementation. The ratio per technician has decreased significantly compared to the previous year because this is the first year that we have another full-time sustainability technician, with two full-time figures now in the sustainability project.

28 external certification audits have been carried out in Spain, Portugal, Italy and Chile. 23 of these were recertification audits, **5 in new locations**, all in different oil mills. This means that 100% of the oil mills included in the project, in addition to being audited internally, have been audited externally by Intertek.

During 2024, pre-audits were carried out prior to the certification audits, with the aim of measuring the work of implementing the protocol by Deoleo technicians

and preparing for the external audit. In 2024, 25 pre-audits were carried out, corresponding to **408 hours**, which represents 51 days spent by the technicians. **152 more pre-audit hours have been carried out than in 2023, a clear indicator that we now have more than one sustainability technician dedicated 100% to the sustainability project.**

During 2024, interviews with farmers have continued to be conducted to complete the mapping of the field. To do this, the farmers' farms have been visited in person. With these interviews, we obtain a global vision of our farmers'

soil management and propose specific actions, such as holding Workshops.

These visits also reinforce the presence of Deoleo technicians in the field. In total, **174 questionnaires have been carried out in 2024, adding to the data from previous years, we have a total sample of 897 farmers interviewed.**

According to samples carried out for surveys by the Andalusian government, we see that they carry out an average characterization of 600 farmers, Therefore, we surpassed all the samplings carried out by public entities. In addition, it should be said that, at the beginning of the project, we proposed to carry out a characterization of at least 10 farmers per oil mill. Currently, in 2024, this objective has already been met in 69% of the oil mills adhering to the sustainability project. With this characterization, a sampling has been obtained in 2024 of 3,069 Has (2024). **Of the sampling carried out in 2024, 5% is Organic, 6.57% in integrated production and 88.47% in Conventional. The number of farmers in API has decreased since these aids have been removed and many of these farmers have returned to conventional, but with integrated management.**

Adding the data of hectares visited in 2024 to those of previous years, the total number of hectares visited by Deoleo technicians is approximately **19,651 hectares, which represents 5.81% of the total hectares under the project.**

To put this data into context, it should be noted that the hectare/member ratio in the olive groves participating in the project is approximately 5.67 hectares per member, and taking into account that this data includes visits to some of the majority members in some oil mills, this means that in order to increase the percentage of hectares visited in a short period of time, the number of visits that must be made is very high.

Regarding the number of hectares visited to intensive and traditional olive groves in the different groups, it has increased considerably, with “3,069” hectares visited in 2024, a total of 19,651.99 hectares have been visited since the sustainability project began. In 2024, 819 more hectares have been visited compared to 2023, which highlights the work of the sustainability technicians and the hiring of the new sustainability technician in 2023.

% of olive groves visited by groups in 2024

As we can see in the graph, the field characterization carried out in Almaliva, Viñaoliva, Olivomundo, Jaencoop, Aceites Canoliva and the new ones in Chile stand out.

INTERNAL INDICATORS

With all the information that Deoleo technicians have collected during this year 2024 and what had already been obtained in previous years, a series of indicators have been compiled to measure the performance of the oil mills and to be able to concentrate efforts and schedule actions for next year. These indicators are divided into 4 large blocks: Organization and people, Quality and food safety, management of resources and waste, and finally use of agrochemicals, biodiversity and soil.

Organization and people:

In 2024, we can say that the oil mills participating in the project have assumed sustainability

within their management policy and have improved their organization and professionalization, in terms of investment planning, strategic plans, cost calculation, security improvement, conciliation plans and computer maintenance. Also noteworthy from a social point of view is the equality aspect, the percentage of oil mills with equality plans has increased from 2% to 26% since the

start of the project. Equality agreements have also been implemented, currently 93% have equality agreements, 4% more than in the previous campaign. Regarding training, in the last year technical and/or management skills have been promoted, currently 29% of suppliers have provided technical training compared to 20% in the previous campaign. Regarding the definition of preventive resources, we currently have 81% of oil mills that have conciliation plans, 14% more improvement than in the previous campaign. 92% of our suppliers have already defined inventories of service companies, promoting local employment and the value of rural and local communities.

*All indicators refer to the percentage of oil mills that meet the requirements.

Food quality and safety:

This sector includes the production and food safety part of the oil mill. The installation of covered receiving hoppers has improved, adding up to a 17.1% improvement since the start of the project. The records of the mixing time have meant an improvement of 86.5% since the start of the project. Regarding the use of food belts, the percentage of oil mills with 100% food belts has increased by 2.1% compared to 2023. 88.5% of suppliers have already identified chemical hazards within their HACCP, 6.8% more than in 2023. The number of oil mills with magnets has also increased, 8.5% more than in 2023.

Regarding the quality of EVOO production, at the beginning of the project there was a lack of control and records of fundamental parameters for quality that allow us to identify weak points in order to take measures. There has been a very notable increase in the number of olive oil mills that have begun to record all quality parameters. Regarding the use of adjuvants, the percentage of olive oil mills that record talc batches has improved by 32.5%.

Resource and waste management:

This sector includes the efficient management of resources (Water and Energy), as well as the correct management of waste and the recovery of by-products.

In this area, the oil mills at the start of the project had a very high margin for improvement, only 20% of them recorded water consumption and 14% had some kind of savings plan, now in 2024, 97.7% record water consumption and have a water saving plan, with regard to energy the figures are similar, now 98.9% have a savings plan, which has meant an improvement of 16.9% compared to 2023 and 100% record their energy consumption, both outside and during the campaign. Regarding the carbon footprint, a notable improvement has been noted during 2024, currently 8% of the oil mills have calculated their carbon footprint (2% more than in the previous campaign). Regarding the use of renewable energy sources, currently 44.8% of suppliers use renewable energy sources, 4.6% more than in 2023.

In 2024, all the oil mills are already registered as small producers and have a contract with an authorized waste manager. The management of this waste and its storage has also improved significantly, 100% of the oil mills have their waste well stored and managed. During this year 2024, 31% of oil mills have implemented training in waste management, 6.9% of oil mills manage firewood and 9.19% have compost plants.

Use of agrochemicals, biodiversity and soil:

One of the keys to reducing the use of agrochemicals in olive groves and thus preventing the loss of biodiversity is the importance of each olive mill having an independent field technician who advises the partners on their treatments, as well as issuing prescriptions for authorized agrochemicals with controlled and rational doses. At this point, since

the beginning of the project, 7 field technicians have been hired by the groups, mainly these hires have been by the Jaencoop group and the Almaliva Group, and in the 2024_2025 campaign, two new hires have been added, one by the Biolivamed Company Group, and another by the Greek oil mills, which will provide training in food safety and quality in the oil mills.

During this year 2024, training sessions have been held to promote the use of plant cover, prevent soil erosion, preserve the biodiversity of olive groves, use of by-products such as compost, etc. A total of **14 workshops have been held within the framework of the Soil O-live project and some collaborations with other entities** such as CETAEX in Extremadura, or the Tierra Creativa foundation in the municipality of Villanueva de Córdoba. In total, more than **300 farmers have participated.**

At field level, the changes are much more difficult, as they often affect cultural changes, such as the establishment of vegetation cover in Extremadura, for example, or in some areas of Seville, as well as other actions related to the fight against soil erosion and the restoration or conservation of biodiversity. To make progress in this regard, we have concentrated the measures on the biodiversity plans, for which in 2024, minutes have been drawn up to review the biodiversity plan, with commitments by the groups and oil mills to carry out specific measures with a date of execution.

These measures range from the establishment of plant covers, actions for reforestation with native flora, installation of nesting boxes or insect hotels, holding workshops, etc.

Example: Almaliva Group Biodiversity Plan

ANEXO IV: COMPROMISO DE LA ALMAZARA

Aceites CANOLIVA S.L. está comprometido en la conservación de la biodiversidad y características originales de los espacios naturales en los que se desarrolla la actividad de Extracción de aceite de Oliva Virgen Extra y sobre los que tiene influencia. Por ello, se compromete a dar visibilidad al presente Plan de Acción de Conservación de la Biodiversidad y, en caso necesario, establecer medidas correctoras, para la conservación del olivar como ecosistema, su fauna y flora, que forman parte de la biodiversidad propia de la región de España donde se localiza.

Es deseo, por tanto, de Aceites CANOLIVA S.L. hacer partícipes a todos los grupos de interés de la importancia de involucrarse en proyectos que fomenten la biodiversidad natural y original del capital natural existente en las comarcas de la denominación de origen de Baena, como medida de comprobada eficacia para aumentar nuestra resiliencia a los efectos del calentamiento global. En este sentido, este Plan de Acción queda a disposición de todas las partes interesadas con el objetivo de ejercer un papel ejemplificador que impulse nuevas iniciativas sostenibles en las organizaciones de la zona.

Y para que así conste, firmo y sello:

Dña. María Cano, en Representación a Aceites CANOLIVA S.L.

En Baena a 03 de Julio de 2024

7. OBJETIVOS ESTABLECIDOS PARA LAS MEDIDAS DE CONSERVACIÓN DE LA BIODIVERSIDAD

Medida	Responsable	Plazo	Descripción situación de partida	Descripción de la situación deseada	Objetivo a corto-medio plazo
1º. Asesorar y transferir conocimientos a los agricultores.		Continuo	Muchos agricultores desconocen la legislación vigente y realiza las labores y tratamientos fitosanitarios según costumbres de la zona.	Los agricultores se informan de los tratamientos fitosanitarios y las labores a realizar por consejo técnico.	Uno de los objetivos propuestos es la realización de jornadas de formación sobre uso racional de agroquímicos y fomento de biodiversidad en los olivares.
2º. No emplear herbicidas o usar el mínimo posible.		Continuo	Agricultores con falta de formación emplean herbicidas superando las dosis y no respetando el ancho de cubiertas.	Emplear el mínimo herbicida posible o dejar de emplearlo en las zonas que sea posible.	Como objetivo se establece la realización de 1 Jornada al menos cada 2 años Deoleo con OLEAND.
3º. Instaurar y diversificar las cubiertas vegetales.	Técnico/a de campo interno/externo	Continuo	Existen zonas en las que se tienen cubiertas vegetales homogéneas.	Diversificar cubiertas vegetales (aumentar biodiversidad)	Fomentar el uso de la implantación de la cubierta vegetal en zonas con baja pendiente donde no es un requisito legal, mediante jornadas de formación. Como objetivo se establece el aumento progresivo de la cubierta vegetal, se verificará anualmente con las visitas de los técnicos de campo el cumplimiento de las medidas. Se propone exponer una muestra de 5 socios anuales nuevos con cubierta vegetal.

Example of a Biodiversity Plan by Oleand Manzanilla Olive and Canoliva Oils S.L.

It is also worth noting that, from the characterization carried out in 2024, 97% of the farmers interviewed have maintained the vegetation cover, 9% have installed some functional element for fauna such as feeders or drinkers, 94.59% maintain the boundaries on their farm, and 93% have technical advice. 94.7% of the surface visited has pruning remains on the farm. In 17% of the farms, the stone walls are maintained.

In 2024, the percentage of oil mills issuing advisory bulletins and recipes to their partners, or the number of oil mills with hired field technicians, has also increased.

STATUS BY GROUPS/OIL MILLS

In this section, key people in each oil mill and farmers will be analyzed and detailed, as well as the degree of involvement of the oil mills, and practices that can be extrapolated to other groups or oil mills will also be identified.

GENERAL

During this year, a constant and progressive improvement has been noted in all groups from the GAP to the external audit. During 2024, 21 internal audits have also been carried out (2 Portugal, 6 Almaliva, 5 InterOleo, 5 Jaencoop, 3 Viñaoliva), all of them with satisfactory results. These mills will be renewed as sustainable suppliers in 2025.

GOOD PRACTICES FIELD

Below are some of the good practices carried out in some of the farms participating in the project. Only images of the certified/visited olive oil mills in 2024 are shown.

PRACTICE	EVIDENCE	PRACTICE	EVIDENCE
Infiltrators, efficient irrigation system. (S. Coop del Campo San Isidro, Valencia del Ventoso)			
Sown vegetation cover (S. Coop San Isidro, Villafranca de los Barros)			
Installation of artificial nests (S. Coop Ntra Sra de la Cabeza, Fuente del Maestre)			
Installation of artificial drinking troughs (SCA Aceites de Sierra de Yeguas)			

<p>Maintenance of vegetation cover (Puricon SCA)</p>			
<p>Equine Grazing (Olivomundo)</p>			
<p>Maintenance of vegetation cover (Oleand Manzanilla Olive)</p>			
<p>Islands of biodiversity on the farm Explotaciones Pepe Cano S.L (Aceites Canoliva S.L)</p>			

<p>Creation of a sustainable space/garden with aromatic plants (Santa Marina de Aguas Santas, Fernán Núñez)</p>			
<p>Reforestation with native species (Santa Marina de Aguas Santas, Fernán Núñez)</p>			
<p>Installation of water troughs for horses in Olivarera los Pedroches</p>			
<p>Maintenance of tall trees (SCA Ntra Sra de Luna, Villanueva de Córdoba)</p>			

<p>Natural microclimate (SCA Our Lady of Consolation, Doña Mencia)</p>			
<p>Maintenance of boundaries (SCA Cerro Gordo, Ventorros de San José)</p>			
<p>Maintenance of vegetation cover (SCA Olivarrera y Cerealista San Sebastián)</p>			
<p>Installation of insect hotels (SCA Olivarrera de Lucena)</p>			

<p>Infographics on field management improvements (SCA Ntra Sra de Guadalupe)</p>			
<p>Conservation of native flora (SCA San Francisco, VVA)</p>			
<p>Application of organic matter (SCA Vera Cruz, VVA)</p>			
<p>Maintenance of vegetation cover (SCA Los Toscares, Venta de los Santos)</p>			
<p>Maintenance of vegetation cover (SCA San Isidro, Iznatoraf)</p>			

<p>Installation of artificial nests (SCA Cristo de la Salud, Villargordo)</p>			
<p>Installation of artificial nests at SCA Gutamarta, Cortijos Nuevos.</p>			
<p>Installation of artificial nests for Our Lady of Nazareth, Chiclana de Segura</p>			
<p>Installation of artificial nest at SCA San Isidro Labrador, Benatae.</p>			
<p>Installation of an artificial nest at SCA Santa Teresa de Jesus, Beas de Segura.</p>			

<p>Cattle grazing in Aceites Carrascal, Torres de Albánchez.</p>			
<p>Flood control. SCA Bedmarese.</p>			
<p>Installation of artificial drinking troughs at SCA Bedmarese.</p>			
<p>Maintenance of natural nests at SCA San Isidro Labrador de Canena.</p>			

<p>Installation of solar panels, artificial nests and ponds in Oleocampo SCA.</p>			
<p>Maintenance of vegetation cover in SCA La Unión de Bujalance.</p>			
<p>Maintenance of the vegetation cover at SCA San Juan, Villargordo.</p>			
<p>Maintenance of solar panels in Ntra Sra del Rosario, Charilla.</p>			
<p>Organic olive grove (Mavrogenis)</p>			

<p>Maintenance of Biodiversity Islands in Carmen, Confoliva.</p>			
<p>Use of Boxes in Casale, Unapol.</p>			

GOOD PRACTICES OIL MILL

Below, some of the good practices carried out at Almazara in 2024 are presented in images.

VIÑAOLIVA			
OLIVE MILL AND IMPROVEMENT	EVIDENCE	OLIVE MILL AND IMPROVEMENT	EVIDENCE
<p>Holding of a company committee in S. Coop San Isidro, Entrin Bajo.</p>			
<p>Implementation of a strategic plan at S. Coop Viñaoliva, Almendralejo.</p>			

<p>Installation of food grade bands in Ntra Sra de la Cabeza, Fuente del Maestre.</p>			
<p>Installation of solar panels (S. Coop San Isidro, Valencia del Ventoso)</p>			
<p>Creation of an equality committee. (S. Coop San Isidro, Villafranca de los Barros)</p>			
<p>ALMALIVA</p>			
<p>Taking water meter readings (SCA Santa Marina de Aguas Santas)</p>			
<p>Data automatización (Almazaras de la Subbética)</p>			

<p>Automation of the process by telephone application (Almazara de Luque SCA)</p>			
<p>IFS Certification (Olive grove Ntra Sra de Luna, Villanueva de Córdoba)</p>			
<p>Start of the management of pesticide waste from farmers (Sigfito and Valorfito) (SCA Ntra Sra de la Salud, Castro del Río)</p>			
<p>Record of energy consumption by production unit (SCA Virgen de la Torre)</p>			
<p>Firewood management at SCA Cerro Gordo, Ventorros de San José</p>			

<p>Start of the use of biofertilizers (SCA Olivarera de Lucena)</p>			
<p>Implementation of equality measures. (SCA San Isidro, Loja)</p>			
<p>JAENCOOP</p>			
<p>Installation of solar panels (Our Lady of Guadalupe, Úbeda)</p>			
<p>Solar panel installation (SCA San Francisco, Villanueva del arzobispo)</p>			
<p>Vehicle flow control (SCA Vera Cruz, Villanueva del Arzobispo)</p>			

<p>Analysis of production cost trends (SCA Gutamarta, Cortijos nuevos)</p>			
<p>Definition of a sustainability manager (SCA San Blas, Sorihuela del Guadalimar)</p>			
<p>ecoWorld system certification, sustainability and ecology (ozone disinfection) (SCA San Marcos, Beas de Segura)</p>			
<p>ACEITES CANOLIVA S.L.</p>			
<p>Bulk filtration (Aceites Canoliva S.L.)</p>			
<p>MOLINO DEL GENIL-FITAGRO</p>			
<p>Winery expansion (Lagar do Sobrado)</p>			

PURICON SCA			
Impeccable order and cleanliness (Puricon SCA)			
ACEITES DE SIERRA DE YEGUAS			
Forecast for remodeling the patio (Aceites de Sierra de Yeguas)			
OLEAND MANZANILLA OLIVE			
Water consumption records (Oleand Manzanilla Olive)			
INTEROLEO			
Start of firewood management (SCA Ntra Sra de los Remedios, Jimena)			
Floating Photovoltaic Solar Plant (Almazara la Loma)			
Carbon footprint calculation (Almazara la Loma)			

<p>Guide for equal opportunities between men and women (SCA La Unión de Bujalance)</p>			
<p>Installation of solar panels (SCA Oleícola Baeza)</p>			
<p>Installation of equality posters (Cambil Olive Oil Union)</p>			
<p>Implementation of Occupational Risk Prevention (Korbakis)</p>			
<p>Establishment of a site for the storage of hazardous waste (Korbakis)</p>			
<p>Training in Quality and Sustainability (Casale, Unapol)</p>			

WORKSHOP OIL MILLS SUSTAINABILITY PROJECT

During 2024, 14 Workshops have been held in different cooperatives adhering to the sustainability project within the framework of the European Soil O-Live project, with the first Workshop in Portugal as a novelty. In addition, we have collaborated with CETAEX in a training session, we have participated in a planting day with children from the municipality of Villanueva del arzobispo, and we have participated in a training session with the collaboration of the Tierra Creativa foundation and the Ntra Sra de Luna cooperative. In addition, we have collaborated in some sessions with UPA. Below is a summary table of the Workshops held:

JAENCOOP			
SCA San Juan de la Cruz, Beas de Segura			
SCA Ntra Sra de Guadalupe, Úbeda			
Planting Day in Villanueva del Arzobispo.			

ALMALIVA			
<p>Ntra Sra de la Salud, Castro del Río</p>			
<p>Olivarera y Cerealista San Sebastián, San Sebastián de los ballesteros</p>			
<p>Jornada Tierra Creativa, Villanueva de Córdoba</p>			
INTEROLEO			
<p>SCA Bedmarese</p>			

<p>SCA San Isidro Labrador de Canena</p>			
--	---	--	---

VIÑAOLIVA

<p>S. Coop San Isidro, Villafranca de los Barros.</p>			
---	---	---	---

<p>Conference at CETAEX, Villafranco del Gudiana.</p>			
---	---	---	---

Aceites de Sierra de Yeguas

<p>Workshop en Aceites de Sierra de Yeguas.</p>			
---	---	---	---

LAGAR DO SOBRADO, PORTUGAL

Workshop en
Lagar Do Sobrado

Workshop en
Lagar Do
Sobrado

CONFERENCES IN COLLABORATION WITH UPA

Through this renewed partnership, we are dedicated to supporting traditional olive producers. A good example is our support for Cubiwood, an innovative project aimed at increasing vegetation cover for woody crops in Spain. By improving soil management in agricultural areas, we can reduce the risks posed by climate change in vulnerable regions.

Seville. *150 young farmers and ranchers from across Spain came together to address critical issues such as improving rural profitability, improving access to land and water, reducing bureaucratic barriers and empowering older farmers to help prepare the next generation in shaping the future of agriculture.*

PRIMER CONGRESO IGUALDAD DE OLEO "CRECIENDO JUNTAS"

ALMALIVA

Since joining the sustainability project, it can be said that involvement is maximum, the staff is fully involved and they have a team of field and sustainability technicians that make it easier to implement all the requirements of the sustainability protocol, both at the oil mill and field level.

Thanks to Deoleo's sustainability protocol, new field technicians have been hired.

During 2024, five oil mills have been recertified, specifically (Almazaras de la Subbética, Santa Marina de Aguas Santas, Almazara de Luque, Ntra Sra de Luna de Villanueva de Córdoba and Olivarera los Pedroches). Internal audits have also been carried out on the oil mills that are due for renewal in 2025, specifically, 6 internal audits have been carried out, and follow-ups have been carried out on all the oil mills that were renewed in 2023.

In this year 2024, field characterization has been enhanced, visiting a total of **265.33 Has.**

Regarding biodiversity, work has been done on farm evaluation checklists to determine the surface area of ecological interest. Seven farmers have been selected from each oil mill and recertified, and an internal audit has been carried out. New farms will be selected annually and measures will be implemented to improve biodiversity on these farms.

The implementation of workshops in collaboration with the group has continued to be promoted over the last year, specifically training sessions have been held in the municipalities of Castro del Río, Pozoblanco and San Sebastián de los Ballesteros.

As a novelty, it is also worth highlighting that, in the last part of the year, two oil mills of the Almaliva group (SCA

Cerro Gordo and San Isidro de Loja) have decided to leave the Almaliva group, but we will work in the first part of 2025 to ensure that they continue within our sustainability project.

STRENGTHS: INVOLVEMENT and PROACTIVITY, AGROCHEMICALS (team of technicians), BIODIVERSITY.

WEAK POINTS: FOOD SAFETY (this part is being reinforced in some oil mills with technical advice from Almaliva group)

OBJETIVOS ESTABLECIDOS PARA LAS MEDIDAS DE CONSERVACIÓN DE LA BIODIVERSIDAD.

Cooperativa:

- > 1º. Asesorar y transferir conocimientos a los agricultores y
- > 2º. No emplear herbicidas o usar el mínimo posible.

	Asesorar y transferir conocimientos a los agricultores.		No emplear herbicidas o usar el mínimo posible.	
	Nombre de los cursos de asistencia de los técnicos.	Cálculo del porcentaje de incremento o decremento con respecto a la campaña anterior	Nombre de los cursos dados a los agricultores	Cálculo del porcentaje de incremento o decremento con respecto a la campaña anterior
Objetivos realizados en la campaña 2021/2022	DF-INNOVA. Regeneración de suelos, fertilización, y mejora eficiencia en la fertilización nitrogenada. 15/11/2022	100 % (covid en campaña anterior)	REDUCCIÓN APLICACIÓN HERBICIDAS Regeneración de suelos, reducción de herbicidas y mejora eficiencia. 15/11/2022	100 % (covid en campaña anterior)
Objetivos propuestos para la campaña 2022/2023	- Charla de cubiertas vegetales. - Charla abonado. - Mejora eficiencia de riego		-Charla de reducción del uso y mejora en la eficiencia de aplicación de herbicidas.	

Example of Almaliva review minutes.

1. INDIQUE EL NÚMERO, LONGITUD O SUPERFICIE DE CADA ELEMENTO SIE									
Type de SIE	*Condiciones principales (consulte las condiciones precisas para cada tipo) *	"Cantidad y unidad" (tenga cuidado de no contar dos veces entre hectáreas -ha-, son -a- y centiare -ca)			Fact. Conv	Total (m ²)			
Setos o franjas leñosas	Ancho máximo ≤ 10 m	0			m lineal	10	0		
Arboles aislados	Couronne ≥ 4 m OU arbre têtard				árbol (s)	30	0		
Árboles alineados	*Cada árbol respeta las condiciones Árbol aislado (ver arriba) Y espacio entre coronas mínimo de 5 m *	0			m lineal	10	0		
arboledas	Superficie ≤ 10 áreas	0	ha	0	a	0	ca (= m ²)	1,5	0
	10 áreas < superficie ≤ 30 áreas	0	ha	0	a	0	ca (= m ²)	1,5	0
Estanques	*No artificializado (ni hormigón ni plástico) Y superficie máxima ≤ 10 áreas	0	ha	0	a	0	ca (= m ²)	1,5	0
Zanjas	*No artificializado (ni hormigón ni plástico) Y ancho máximo ≤ 6 m *	0			m lineal	6	0		
Paredes de piedra tradicionales	*Piedra natural sin hormigón Y 0.5 m ≤ altura ≤ 2 m Y 0.1 m ≤ ancho ≤ 2 m *	0			m lineal	1	0		

Checklist Area of ecological interest

OLIVE MILL	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
FERNAN NUÑEZ	CREATING A SUSTAINABLE GARDEN
LA SUBBETICA	CALCULATION OF THE WATER AND CARBON FOOTPRINT, WORK IS BEING UNDERTAKEN ON ISO 14001 CERTIFICATION WITH CAVALA SOLUTIONS
LUQUE	DIGITALIZATION BY APPLYING QUALITY DATA
POZOBLANCO	CREATING A STORE SPACE WITH LOCAL PRODUCTS
VILLANUEVA DE CÓRDOBA	HIRING A QUALITY TECHNICIAN.
BUJALANCE	INSTALLING AN ELECTRIC CHARGING POINT
CASTRO DEL RÍO	REMODELING OF THE FACTORY BODY
DOÑA MENCIA	INSTALLATION OF 100% OF FOOD BELTS
LA VICTORIA	CREATING A SUSTAINABLE GARDEN
ALBENDIN	CARRYING OUT METER READINGS BIWEEKLY
CERRO GORDO	CALCULATION OF THE CARBON FOOTPRINT THROUGH FAECA
NUEVA CARTEYA	READINGS OF THE WATER METER FOR THE MAINS AND WELL WATER EVERY BIWEEK
SAN SEBASTIAN DE LOS BALLESTEROS	PATIO REMODELING

OLIVARERA LUCENA	DE	TRAINING ON CARBON FOOTPRINT AND USE OF BIOFERTILIZERS
SCA SAN ISIDRO, LOJA		APPLICATION OF COMPOST, INSTALLATION OF ARTIFICIAL NESTS ON MEMBERS' FARMS AND IMPLEMENTATION OF EQUALITY PLAN.

JAENCOOP

Jaencoop Group is a clear example of excellence in quality, thus promoting early harvesting, with some of its own brands such as Prólogo or Saqura. Likewise, in 2024 the Biodiversity Plan was revised, with a biodiversity plan review report being drawn up. Since the start of the project, 5 field technicians have already been hired.

The 8 cooperatives recertified during the 2024/2025 campaign have significantly improved their waste management, cooperative organization, records of oil quality parameters and commitments to specific actions to improve, and with the support of Deoleo and Jaencoop technicians, their recertification has been achieved. During 2024, all the oil mills already certified in previous years have been monitored, and, in addition, 5 internal audits have been carried out on those certified in 2022, which will be renewed as a sustainable supplier in 2025.

During 2024, Deoleo and Grupo Jaencoop have collaborated in a massive plantation/reforestation with native species and in collaboration with children from the municipality and with the sponsorship of the Villanueva del Arzobispo town council, which has obtained the plants. Four training sessions/workshops have also been held for farmers in

affiliated oil mills.

Work has also been done with technicians to update the API memory and the analysis, although the number of farmers in API has decreased due to the withdrawal of aid.

During this year 2024, the characterization of the field has also continued, visiting the farms of farmers belonging to the group, adding up to a total, only in the year 2024, of **277.77 Has.**

INFORME ACTUACIONES REALIZADAS PARA LA "ACTUALIZACIÓN Y SEGUIMIENTO DEL PLAN DE BIODIVERSIDAD" JAENCOOP 2024	
FECHA	31 de julio de 2024
ALMAZARA	GRUPO JAENCOOP 2º GRADO SCA
ASISTENTES	PROJAEN <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JUAN MARTOS LORITE • LAURA FERNÁNDEZ LÓPEZ • JOSÉ VERA • JOSE MANUEL MARTINEZ MEDINA • MARIO ANAYA VIVO • ANTONIO GONZÁLEZ LUCHA JAENCOOP <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TOÑI FERNÁNDEZ HERNÁNDEZ

Image: Review of the Jaencoop Biodiversity Plan

During 2024, technical training has also been provided by the Jaencoop group, technical day your oil mill your future.

ACTIVIDAD FORMATIVA GRATUITA DIRIGIDA A

MAESTROS DE ALMAZARA
PERSONAL TÉCNICO
DIRECTIVOS

JAENCOOP SCA 2º GRADO

TE ESPERAMOS!!!

Fecha: Jueves 27 de junio de 2024
Lugar de celebración: Sede JAENCOOP en Puente de Génave
Horario: 09:00h a 14:00h

Contenidos:

- Mesa de trabajo 1: Agricultura de precisión
HEMAV y BURGOS SALAVERRY
- Mesa de trabajo 2: Calidad y Seguridad Alimentaria
 - Descubriendo el potencial del NIR en el proceso de extracción de Aceite de Oliva (ISR)
 - La refrigeración de pastas de aceituna para la obtención de AOVES de máxima calidad (MENXI)
 - Decanter IMPELLER (MANZANO-FLOTTWEG)
- DESCANSO-COFFEE BREAK
- Mesa de trabajo 3: Gestión de residuos y buenas prácticas (MANUEL HIGUERAS, TÉCNICO DEPARTAMENTO DE CALIDAD DE COOPERATIVAS AGROALIMENTARIAS DE JAÉN)
- Mesa de trabajo 4: Liderazgo y trabajo en equipo. Buenas prácticas (ADELA REINA, TÉCNICA DE FORMACIÓN E IGUALDAD DE COOPERATIVAS AGROALIMENTARIAS DE JAÉN)

*Al final de la actividad formativa, recuperamos fuerzas con un aperitivo.

Para confirmar asistencia, envía un mensaje a
Toñi Fernández Hernández
Dirección de Producción de Almazaras
almazaras@jaencoop.com
697 306 036

JAENCOOP SCA. NIF: 705441111. C.I.F. F32001000

Ayuda de Valencia en
20300 Vía del Arcoiris, Jaén (Spain)
T: +34 952 461 030
www.jaencoop.com

STRENGTHS: High commitment from the group since the beginning of the project. Improvements have been made in Quality, document management system, and Biodiversity.

WEAK POINTS: Waste management is still in its initial phase in many oil mills.

MILL	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
NTRA SRA DE GUADALUPE	Hiring a quality and sustainability technician.
NTRA SRA DEL PILAR	Implementation of a workplace harassment protocol and equality plan.
SCA SAN FRANCISCO VVA	ISO 22,000 Certification. Equality workshops, Creating Networks.
SCA SAN ISIDRO VVA	Installation of electric charging point.
VERA CRUZ VVA	Use of certified bone.
LA UNION DE CHILLUEVAR	Implementation of a work-life balance plan.
LOS TOSCARES, VENTA DE LOS SANTOS	Definition of a sustainability manager.
SAN FRANCISCO, ARROYO DEL OJANCO	Communication of the right to collective bargaining/Installation of an electric charging point.

SAN ISIDRO DE IZNATORAF	Request for a quote for the installation of solar panels.
SAN JUAN DE LA CRUZ	Taking water meter readings every two weeks.
ACEITES ZÁRATE	Appointment of a preventive resource
GUTAMARTA	Installation of solar panels
LA VICARÍA	Renovation of the reception patio
NTRA SRA DE NAZARET	Digital Kit
SAN BLAS, SORIHUELA DEL GUADALIMAR	Implementation of a work-life balance plan.
SAN ISIDRO LABRADOR, BENATAE	Purchase of land for new ponds.
SAN MARCOS	Sustainability and Ecology EcoWorld.
SANTA TERESA	Carbon footprint calculation.
CRISTO DE LA SALUD	Execution of a hazardous waste treatment contract
ACEITES EL CARRASCAL	Renovation of the olive reception patio
SCA SAN JUAN BAUTISTA	Getting started in hazardous waste management

INTEROLEO

Currently in 2024, we have 16 certified oil mills from the InterOleo group. During 2024, follow-ups have been carried out on all the already certified oil mills, as well as implementation visits to the oil mills that were due for renewal, since, as a novelty, in 2024, the first renewal audits of the certified oil mills in 2021 have been carried out.

During 2024, internal audits have also continued to be held, with a total of 5 internal audits corresponding to the oil mills certified in 2022. Also worth noting is the holding of 3 Workshops, at the oil mills of SCA Bedmarensense, SCA San Isidro Labrador de Canena and SCA La Unión de Bujalance, with the collaboration of the UJA and the Soil O-live project for their holding.

At the field level, a review of the biodiversity plan has been carried out in 2024, although the field remains its main weak point, as it does not have hired field technicians, although it has recently signed an agreement with BALAM Agriculture to improve advice to the partner. Also, it

is worth highlighting the great progress made in waste management, when we began to work with the group, the majority did not manage waste properly, and all of them now have a contract for the treatment of hazardous waste, although in some cases their segregation can still be improved.

During 2024, field characterization has also continued among the partners that are part of the InterOleo group, making visits to more than 169 hectares of olive groves. Biodiversity measures have also continued to be implemented through collaboration with Seo Birdlife.

Also worth mentioning is the floating photovoltaic plant that has been built in Almazara La Loma, on the Cortijo Guadiana estate.

Illustration of the floating photovoltaic plant Almazara la Loma S.L.

	<p>REVISIÓN PLAN BIODIVERSIDAD INTEROLEO</p>	<p>FECHA DE EDICIÓN: 28/11/2024</p>	
<p>1. CUBIERTA VEGETAL/ MINIMIZACIÓN DEL LABOREO</p>		<p>Grupo InterOleo, tiene una apuesta clara por la recuperación de la biodiversidad. Se está trabajando con el programa cultiva carbono, programa que se desarrolla desde el departamento de Balam Nature. Programa que incentiva a los agricultores a la adopción de prácticas de agricultura de carbono adicionales para la reducción de los gases de efecto invernadero. Además, los técnicos de Deoleo han realizado muestreos en campo en 2024, en concreto se han entrevistado 30 agricultores que forman parte de InterOleo, suponiendo un área de 169 Has de olivar caracterizadas, en la mayoría de las explotaciones se mantiene la cubierta vegetal. En 2025 se seguirán potenciando las visitas de campo, y se seguirá potenciando la cubierta vegetal entre los socios que forman parte de grupo InterOleo.</p>	
<p>2. COLABORACIÓN CON ASOCIACIONES</p>		<p>Grupo InterOleo, colabora con la fundación SEO BIRD LIFE, realizando prácticas de restauración y sostenibilidad, como la instalación de nidos artificiales, instalación de bebederos, hoteles de insectos, reforestación con aromáticas en bordes, etc. Estas prácticas se están desarrollando en almazaras como SCA Bedmarensense, Ntra Sra de los Remedios de Jimena, Almazara la Loma, Oleocampo SCA. También se ha realizado un convenio con Peláez Renovables potenciando la valorización del hueso de aceituna de todos los socios que forman parte de grupo InterOleo.</p>	
<p>2. COLABORACIÓN CON ASOCIACIONES</p>		<p>Se ha colaborado con Deoleo, y el proyecto Soil Olive de la Universidad de Jaen, en la celebración de 3 Workshop de asesoramiento a los socios, en colaboración con el grupo InterOleo. Los tres actos, han estado dirigidos a agricultores y expertos del sector, contando con la presencia de expertos de la Universidad de Jaén. Las jornadas han sido abiertas para todos los socios que forman parte del grupo InterOleo. Las mismas se han desarrollado en SCA San Isidro Labrador de Canena, SCA Bedmarensense y SCA La Unión de Bujalance. Como acción a futuro para 2025 se propone hacer extensible estas formaciones.</p>	

Image: InterOleo biodiversity review report

STRENGTHS: ORGANIZATION, FOOD SAFETY.

WEAK POINTS: Communication and willingness on the part of InterOleo group staff when setting dates with the oil mills could be improved; in 2024 this has continued to be its weak point.

MILL	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
Bedmarensense SCA	Collaboration with Seo Bird life for the implementation of measures in favour of biodiversity.
Ntra Sra de los Remedios, Jimena	Creation of a new phytosanitary warehouse/Creation of an equality guide/Creation of an emergency plan
San Gines y San Isidro, Sabiote	Filtration system installation
San Isidro labrador de Canena	Training in programmable automata and social entities.
San Isidro, Pozo Alcón	Hiring women.
Almazara la Loma SL	Technologically advanced oil mill / Construction of a floating solar plant.
Oleocampo SCA	Holding union elections/Providing services to members such as prevention of occupational risks.
SCA La Union de Bujalance	Painting of storage hoppers, installation of thermometer in the warehouse.

Roldan Oliva	Getting started in hazardous waste management
SCA Ntra Sra de la Asunción, Orcera	Start reading the water meter.
SCA Oleícola Baeza	Installation of solar panels
SCA San Juan, Villargordo	Preparation of an annual report on ponds even though it is not mandatory
SCA Union Oleícola Cambil	Hiring new women by 2024.
SCA Ntra Sra de la Misericordia	Start recording the temperature of the cellar
SCA SAN FELIPE APOSTOL	Improvements in quality management.
SCA NTRA SRA DEL ROSARIO, CHARILLA	Definition of preventive recourse in 2024, implementation of equality measures.

VIÑAOLIVA

Despite the limitations in terms of the characteristics of the soil in the area, farmers who want to improve their agro-environmental practices are being located. In 2024, monitoring has been carried out on all the cooperatives in the group, detecting in some of them a considerable increase in olive groves with plant cover, in cooperatives such as (Coop del Campo San Isidro de Valencia del Ventoso, S. Coop Cristo del Arco Toral, or S. Coop San Isidro de Villafranca de los barros).

The cooperatives that initially did not manage their waste properly have now all contracted with a waste manager, and the segregation of their waste, both hazardous and non-hazardous, has improved considerably. Another significant improvement

is that, in 2024, functional elements for wildlife have been installed in the cooperatives that were due for recertification (S. Coop Viñaoliva, S. Coop Santa Marta, S. Coop San Isidro de Entrín and S. Coop Virgen de la Estrella).

Three internal audits have been carried out at the oil mills of Ntra Sra de la Cabeza, Ntra Sra de Perales and S. Coop del Campo San Isidro, which will be recertified in 2024. The Viñaoliva group's commitment to the circular economy should also be highlighted, as it is working on the development of a Biodigestator that will be available and accessible to partners between 2025 and 2026.

It is also worth highlighting that, in its commitment to sustainability, two sustainability workshops have been held, one at S. Coop San Isidro in Villafranca de los Barros, taking advantage of the informative meeting on campaign rules for members, and an informative day has also been held with CETAEX of Extremadura, in Villafranco del Gadiana.

Another improvement worth highlighting is that this year, minutes have been drawn up to review the biodiversity plan of the cooperatives that have been tasked with renewing the sustainability project.

	<p>REVISIÓN PLAN BIODIVERSIDAD VIÑAOLIVA</p>	<p>FECHA DE EDICIÓN: 11/10/2024</p>	
<p>1. CUBIERTA VEGETAL/ MINIMIZACIÓN DEL LABOREO</p>		<p>Durante el último año, los técnicos de Deoleo han observado en sus visitas rutinarias a campo que se están sembrando algunas cubiertas herbáceas, como cubiertas de Girasol, Beza o Colza.</p>	
<p>2. COLABORACIÓN CON ASOCIACIONES</p>		<p>Colaboracion con asociaciones a favor de la igualdad como la Jornada de Socias en Viñaoliva, o el taller de igualdad para agricultoras de la cooperativa S.Coop San Isidro de Entrin, "Mujeres transformando Realidades".</p>	

Image: Example of the minutes of the review of the Viñaoliva biodiversity plan

As an improvement, it is also worth highlighting that during this year 2024, the field characterization has continued, conducting interviews with farmers, adding a total of 179.53 hectares visited in 2024 alone.

STRENGTHS: AGROCHEMICALS, TECHNICAL ADVICE.

WEAK POINTS: BIODIVERSITY, SOIL and QUALITY (Some oil mills have significant improvements in infrastructure).

<p>Mill</p>	<p>EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE</p>
--------------------	---------------------------------------

SAN ISIDRO, ENTRIN	NEW INVESTMENTS, INVESTMENT IN A NEW LINE, NEW HOPPERS, NEW FILTER, NEW OFFICES.
SANTA MARTA	PROVISION OF TRAINING IN EQUALITY AND HARASSMENT PROTOCOL
VIÑAOLIVA	INFRASTRUCTURE IMPROVEMENTS, NEW LINE
VIRGEN DE LA ESTRELLA	DATA AUTOMATION WITH ADAPTIVE SOFTWARE
NTRA SRA DE LA CABEZA	RENOVATION OF THE RECEPTION PATIO, INSTALLATION OF SOLAR PANELS
NTRA SRA DE PERALES	FACTORY EXPANSION, ISO 9001 CERTIFICATION
SAN ISIDRO, VALENCIA DEL VENTOSO	COVER PLANTED ON THE FARMS OF SOME PARTNERS, INSTALLATION OF SOLAR PANELS
SAN ISIDRO, VILLAFRANCA	VEGETABLE COVER PLANTED ON SOME PARTNERS' FARMS
CRISTO DEL HUMILLADERO	EQUALITY TRAINING, NEW FARMS WITH VEGETABLE COVER
CRISTO DEL ARCO TORAL	PARTNERS IN ORGANIC, AND NEW PARTNERS WITH VEGETABLE COVER

SIERRA DE YEGUAS

It is worth highlighting that during 2023, a new manager and sustainability manager was hired, the cooperative was renewed as a sustainable supplier in

2023, and in 2024 the sustainability protocol was monitored. The cooperative's high commitment is also worth highlighting; during 2024, a sustainability workshop was also held, attended by local farmers, as well as local television. During 2024, some farmers who have left their land covered have been located. In the monitoring carried out in 2024, the opportunity was taken to carry out field characterization; 100.87 hectares of olive groves were characterized during the monitoring.

The mill, which did not have any records of quality or management, has begun to collect quality data, such as mixing temperatures, centrifuges, mixing times, hopper residence times, talc, etc. The legality of water collection has also been resolved.

A project is also in the works to make improvements to the reception courtyard.

STRENGTHS: BIODIVERSITY (clear willingness of partners and management to carry out actions)

WEAK POINTS: Infrastructure, uncovered patio, although proactive work is being done to cover it as soon as possible.

Mill	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
ACEITES DE SIERRA DE YEGUAS	PLANTED VEGETABLE COVERS, IMPROVEMENTS IN WATER OPTIMIZATION.

ACEITES CANOLIVA S.L.

During 2024, we have been proactively working with Aceites Canoliva S.L to obtain its certification as a Sustainable supplier. During the month of May 2024, the GAP analysis was carried out, in October the sustainability project was implemented and during the month of November 2024, the supplier Aceites Canoliva S.L was certified as sustainable.

We would like to highlight their clear willingness from the start of the project, and the good foundation we started from, as they have certifications such as BRC, IFS, ECOLOGICAL, KOSHER, etc. Despite this, we have made some progress, such as studying water and energy consumption per production unit, communicating the right to collective bargaining, implementing a sustainability policy and equality agreement. A biodiversity plan has also been drawn up with objectives to be implemented in the coming years.

In the field, it is worth highlighting that the farm visited, a family farm of Explotaciones Pepe Cano, has a high biodiversity value, as it is crossed by a river, and riparian vegetation is maintained, with hedged and intensive olive groves predominating on the farm. In the Baena area, vegetation cover is not a widespread practice, so further work would have to be done on developing it. A sustainability workshop will be held in 2025/2026. During the monitoring that will be carried out in 2025, olive groves in the area of influence of Aceites Canoliva S.L. will be characterized.

Mill	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
ACEITES CANOLIVA S.L.	BRC, IFS, ORGANIC, KOSHER CERTIFICATION.

STRENGTHS: Food quality and safety, organization, high willingness to improve.

WEAK POINTS: Vegetation cover is not so widespread among local farmers who are part of the area of influence of Aceites Canoliva S.L.

OLEAND MANZANILLA OLIVE

During 2024, work has been done to obtain Oleand Manzanilla Olive certification as a sustainable supplier. Specifically, work has begun on two production centers, “Planta las Virtudes” and “Planta San José”, located in the municipality of La Puebla de Cazalla, Seville.

During the month of August 2024, the GAP analysis was carried out, the work plan was established, and a project implementation visit was carried out during the month of October, with certification being obtained in December 2024.

We would like to highlight the high level of involvement of all the staff that has been part of Oleand Manzanilla Olive since the beginning of the project, as well as the good foundation that we started from, since they have certifications such as ISO 9001, ISO 14001, BRC, IFS, Organic and Integrated Production. Despite this, some progress has been made with the implementation of the sustainability project, such as the study of water and energy consumption per production unit, the implementation of a biodiversity plan with specific objectives and action measures in the olive groves under the influence of Oleand Manzanilla Olive, and the unification of the documentation of various areas and departments of the company.

Regarding the field, an improvement has been detected in the use of plant cover, since the practice of tilling is still widespread in the area. In the next visits, field sampling will continue to be carried out to determine the percentage of plant cover in the area. In this initial phase, 26.46 hectares of olive groves have been sampled.

Mill	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
OLEAND MANZANILLA OLIVE	ISO 9001, ISO 14001, BRC, IFS, Ecológico y Producción integrada

STRENGTHS: Food quality and safety, organization, high willingness to improve.

WEAK POINTS: Vegetation cover is not so widespread among local farmers who are part of the Oleand Manzanilla Olive area of influence.

PURICON

Despite being certified in ISO 9001 and ISO 14001, improvements have been made to the quality management system, such as updating the maintenance plan or getting the temperatures and times during grinding to be studied, and even considering taking a quality management course.

In 2023, the cooperative was recertified, with significant improvements such as the signing of the biodiversity plan, or the communication of the right to collective bargaining. In 2024, an annual monitoring of the sustainability project was carried out, taking advantage of it to continue with the field characterization, visiting 65.54 hectares of olive groves in the monitoring. During 2025, an internal audit of the sustainability project will be carried out.

STRENGTHS: AGROCHEMICALS (API available) and WASTE.

WEAK POINTS: BIODIVERSITY and SOIL (the biodiversity plan is still in an initial phase; actions must be developed, and proactivity must be improved in terms of holding training for farmers).

Mill	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
PURICON SCA	LA MAYORIA DE LOS SOCIOS ESTAN EN API, CERTIFICACION ISO 9001, ISO 14001.

MOLINO DEL GENIL-FITAGRO

The work of the quality manager is noteworthy, very attentive and always willing to take action to improve. The group stands out for its continued commitment to sustainability, developing actions such as reforestation with poplars, which is an example of revaluation of a flood zone with a high risk of erosion, an action that can clearly be extrapolated to other cooperatives or groups.

The improvement in waste management is also noteworthy, as this was one of its weak points to date, as well as the start of quality parameter records.

Also noteworthy in Sobrado is the excellent management of resources (Water and Energy) which has been extended to the oil mill since the beginning of the project.

In Molino del Genil, Écija, Spain, monitoring has been carried out during 2024, as it was recertified in 2023. In 2025, we will carry out an internal audit.

In 2024, an internal audit was carried out in Sobrado, as well as a Workshop on the sustainability project for large local farmers.

The group's high commitment to quality and sustainability is worth highlighting. Some improvements have been detected in Sobrado, such as the expansion of the winery.

STRENGTHS: AGROCHEMICALS (GLOBAL GAP), FIELD RESOURCE MANAGEMENT (SENSORS), ORGANIZATION, QUALITY AND FOOD SAFETY.

WEAK POINTS: FUTURE RISK OF HAVING TO RECONVERT THE OLIVE GROVE.

Mill	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
SOBRADO	IRRIGATION MONITORING (IRRIGATION PROBES)
MOLINO DEL GENIL	COMMITMENT TO SUSTAINABILITY (REFORESTATION WITH POPLARS)

OLIVOMUNDO

The involvement of the entire team has been very good from the beginning, its facilities are magnificent, and some quality parameters that are not measured have been updated, a biodiversity plan has been drawn up. During 2024, an internal audit has been carried out in person at the Olivomundo facilities, and in 2025, the recertification of the Sustainability

project will be carried out.

As implemented actions, a sustainability manager (Joao) has been defined, and training has also been provided on the sustainability protocol. In the field, it is worth noting that during the internal audit held in 2024 at Olivomundo, the opportunity was taken to carry out field characterization, specifically 800 Has. were characterized, belonging to the farm, "IMORRIGT, FONTE CANTAROS, AGROPEDRANA"

As for industrial actions, a factory and warehouse expansion is being carried out.

STRENGTHS: AGROCHEMICALS (GLOBAL GAP), WATER MANAGEMENT, ORGANIZATION, QUALITY AND FOOD SAFETY.

WEAK POINTS: ENERGY MANAGEMENT.

MILL	EXTRAPOLABLE EXPERIENCE
OLIVOMUNDO	GLOBAL GAP, WATER MANAGEMENT

GREECE

During 2023, the possibility of expanding to new countries was explored, studying the possibility in Greece, obtaining certification in the oil mills (Kapnas SA, Gargaliani, Korbakis and Mavrogenis, belonging to the Psaroudakis group).

During 2024, the four annual monitoring sessions were carried out, where some improvements were detected in terms of waste management and prevention of occupational risks. The possibility of continuing to expand the certification of olive

oil mills in Greece is being explored. Work is also being done on the development of some Workshops in 2025, specifically two, one in Crete and another in Peloponnese.

Some additional improvements have been detected, such as the hiring of a consultant, who will improve quality in the oil mills, or a new quality manager in Psadourakis.

Strengths: AGROCHEMICAL MANAGEMENT (ORGANIC OLIVE GROVES)

Weaknesses: WASTE MANAGEMENT (THERE ARE NO WASTE MANAGERS IN THE COUNTRY), Occupational Risk Prevention (THERE IS STILL ROOM FOR IMPROVEMENT IN SOME OIL MILLS), FOOD SAFETY.

ITALY

During 2024, remote monitoring has been carried out at the oil mills that were certified in 2023, since due to resources they have had to be carried out remotely.

As a novelty in 2024, two new oil mills have been incorporated into the sustainability project, achieving the AA Gold level of compliance

(Casale and Carmen). In addition, the renewal audit has been carried out at Eurocoop.

As regards quality, maintenance plans have been drawn up, operational records of temperatures and mixing times, and reduction of olive storage time. In all of them, records of water and energy consumption have also been kept.

STRENGTHS: BIODIVERSITY, AGROCHEMICALS AND WASTE

WEAK POINTS: ENERGY MANAGEMENT AND FOOD SAFETY

SUMMARY OF AUDIT SCORES 2024

During 2024, all proposed and planned oil mills have been certified, with **89%** of the certified oil mills obtaining the **AA Gold level** of conformity, and **11%** the **AAA Platinum** level of conformity, (7.9% more oil mills in platinum compared to 2023).

Chart: % audit scores for 2024 sustainability project.

COUNTRY	GROUP	MILL	PUNCTUATION
CH	AGRÍCOLA MONTEOLIVO	AGRÍCOLA MONTEOLIVO	GOLD
ES	JAENCOOP	NTRA SRA DE NAZARET, CHICLANA DE SEGURA	GOLD
ES	JAENCOOP	SCA SAN ISIDRO LABRADOR, BENATAE	GOLD
ES	JAENCOOP	SCA SAN MARCOS, BEAS DE SEGURA	GOLD
ES	JAENCOOP	SCA SANTA TERESA DE JESÚS, BEAS DE SEGURA	GOLD
ES	JAENCOOP	SCA SAN BLAS, SORIHUELA DEL GUADALIMAR	GOLD
ES	JAENCOOP	SCA GUTAMARTA, CORTIJOS NUEVOS	GOLD
ES	VIÑAOLIVA	COOP. VIÑAOLIVA, ALMENDRALEJO	GOLD
ES	VIÑAOLIVA	COOP. SAN ISIDRO, ENTRIN BAJO	GOLD
ES	VIÑAOLIVA	COOP. VIRGEN DE LA ESTRELLA, LOS SANTOS DE MAIMONA	GOLD
ES	VIÑAOLIVA	COOP. SANTA MARTA VIRGEN	GOLD
ES	ACEITES CANOLIVA S.L.	ACEITES CANOLIVA S.L.	GOLD
ES	OLEAND MANZANILLA OLIVE	OLEAND MANZANILLA OLIVE	GOLD
ES	INTEROLEO	SCA BEDMARENSE	GOLD
ES	INTEROLEO	SCA NTRA SRA DE LOS REMEDIOS, JIMENA	GOLD
ES	INTEROLEO	SCA SAN GINES Y SAN ISIDRO, SABIOTE	GOLD
ES	INTEROLEO	SCA SAN ISIDRO LABRADOR DE CANENA	PLATINUM
ES	INTEROLEO	SCA SAN ISIDRO, POZO ALCÓN	GOLD
ES	INTEROLEO	ALMAZARA LA LOMA S.L.	PLATINUM
ES	INTEROLEO	OLEOCAMPO SCA	GOLD
ES	ALMALIVA	SANTA MARINA DE AGUAS SANTAS, FERNAN NUÑEZ	GOLD
ES	ALMALIVA	ALMAZARAS DE LA SUBBÉTICA	PLATINUM
ES	ALMALIVA	ALMAZARA DE LUQUE SCA	GOLD
ES	ALMALIVA	OLIVARERA LOS PEDROCHES, POZOBLANCO	GOLD
ES	ALMALIVA	OLIVARERA NTRA SRA DE LUNA, VILLANUEVA DE CÓRDOBA	GOLD
IT	FINOLIVA	EUROCOOP	GOLD
IT	UNAPOL	CASALE	GOLD
TI	CONFOLIVA	CARMEN	GOLD

Soil O-live PROJECT

During 2022, Deoleo's Sustainability team managed to gain a place in the European Commission, through the Soil O-live project. Project to evaluate the biodiversity and functionality of European olive groves and their relationship with the production and quality of olive oil.

SOIL O-LIVE, led by the University of Jaén, aims to analyse the impact of pollution and land degradation on olive grove soils in terms of multi-biodiversity, investigate the relationship of soil health status with olive oil quality and safety, implement effective soil amendments and ecological restoration practices and define rigorous ecological thresholds to enable future clear standards and regulations to be implemented to design a novel certification for healthy soils in European olive groves.

The project, coordinated with the University of Jaén, has a consortium made up of 17 partners and has funding of almost 7 million euros within the framework of the Soil Health and Food Mission of the Horizon Europe R&D&I program (the European Union's framework program for research and innovation for the period 2021-2027).

In January 2024, Deoleo's sustainability team attended the kick-off meeting held in Mytilene remotely, where the first results of the project were presented. As a novelty, during 2024, the 1st

International Soil O-Live Competition: Soil Health and Quality (The Soil Health & Olive Oil Quality Awards 2024) was held, the first competition in the world that assesses not only the quality of the oils but also the health of the olive grove soils. The awards were presented in Cazorla (Torre del Vinagre), on July 17, 2024. More details in: [Ganadores del I Concurso Internacional Soil O-Live](#)

This first edition was a pilot experience, limited to the 52 farms participating in the Soil O-Live project. For the next edition, it is planned to open participation to more olive farms and commercial partners. The competition was aligned with the EU Strategy for Soil Protection, which seeks to achieve good soil health by 2050 through voluntary and legislative measures. Soil

respiration, one of the evaluation criteria of the competition, is a crucial parameter in the new Soil Monitoring Law, currently in the approval phase by the European Parliament.

During this year 2024, we have been proactively working on the design of a calendar, where farmers were informed of the dates of the next days and encouraged to sustainable practices through famous phrases in each month. The presentation of the calendar and training agenda was presented on March 7, 2024.

Se han repartido en torno a 300 unidades de calendarios entre nuestros agricultores adheridos al proyecto de sostenibilidad.

During this year 2023, active work has been carried out on the project, with the holding of **14 workshops** in different locations in Andalusia, Extremadura and Portugal, with the active participation of more than 300 farmers.

In addition to participating in some additional events, such as collaboration with CETAEX of Extremadura, collaboration with the Jaencoop group in a reforestation where children participated, or collaboration with the Tierra Creativa foundation in a sustainability event in the municipality of Villanueva de Córdoba.

Some of these events have had media coverage in the media:

News of interest for dissemination:

[Jaencoop | Deoleo | Impulsan el Medio Ambiente | Olimerca](#)

[Alumnado de Villanueva del Arzobispo participa en la plantación de 5.000 plantas en terrenos del Grupo Jaencoop](#)

[El proyecto europeo Soil O-Live y Deoleo anuncian 14 formaciones sobre sostenibilidad en 2024 | Mercacei](#)

[Un centenar de agricultores de Jaén y Málaga han participado en dos formaciones sobre sostenibilidad organizadas por el proyecto Soil O-Live y Deoleo - Soil Olive](#)

[El I Concurso de Aceite de Oliva Soil O-Live premia por primera vez la calidad del aceite y la salud del suelo | Diario Digital de la UJA | Compromiso con la sociedad](#)

On November 12 and 13 we attended the European Soil Week in Brussels, Belgium, where we had the opportunity to present our sustainability project.

This event brought together innovators, researchers and policy makers committed to the protection and restoration of this vital resource. It was organised by the European Commission, Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development in the context of the Horizon Europe Mission 'A Deal for Europe's Soil' in collaboration with the Joint Research Centre - EU Soil Observatory and with the support of the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation and the European Research Executive Agency (REA).

During 2025, it is planned to continue holding more workshops in collaboration with the Soil O-live project. The objective for 2025 is to extend these trainings to Italy and Greece, in addition to Spain and Portugal.

Living Soil Project

On October 3, 2024, the Living Soil project was presented at the Caja Rural hall in Jaén, where Deoleo attended, since some of our suppliers, such as the Jaencoop group or Almazaras de la Subbética, are part of it.

The Andalusian Living Lab, with funding of 1,985,990, coordinated by Juan Manuel Jurado, and with a consortium made up of 9 beneficiaries and 7 associates, has as general objectives:

- Address the main challenges related to soil health in olive groves.
- Mitigate the effects of drought - Prevent erosion
- Reduce pollution
- Improve soil structure and biodiversity.

The Andalusian Living Lab will provide economic, technological and logistical support for the implementation of sustainable solutions aimed at improving the state of conservation of the soil of Andalusian olive groves.

The project priorities are:

- Promote solutions for the use of emerging by-products from olive groves and their application to improve soil health.
- Advance digitalization processes to facilitate decision-making (AI)
- Promote business models based on good soil management practices in olive groves (cover planting, sale of carbon credits, etc.)
- Develop innovative solutions to mitigate the structural problem of drought.
- Establish and promote coordinated action plans between the main actors in the value chain in olive oil production.

The consortium is made up of: UJA, INUO, the Regional Government of Andalusia, the Provincial Council of Jaén, IFAPA, Citoliva, the Caja Rural de Jaén Foundation, Jaencoop, Nutesca, Agro-Food Cooperatives, Infaoliva, Finca la Torre, the Subbética Oil Mills, Puerta de las Villas, Cortijo Espíritu Santo, Consul

